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BUSINESS DISCOURSE AS AN INSTITUTIONAL REALITY

Ekaterine Arveladze

Abstract:

The article is dedicated to defining the concept of discourse and business discourse, which is a type of institutional discourse and has a purposeful status-role speech. The article will also present the rules of business etiquette, the need for its knowledge and the characteristics of the institutionalization of business discourse.

Keywords: Discourse, Institutional Discourse, Business Discourse, Business Etiquette.

Introduction:In the age of globalization and information technology, business discourse is a key tool for the development of international business, because it is international business communications that play a special role in the effective and successful business of states, international organizations, transnational corporations, individuals and legal entities. International business relations provide the perception and understanding of the cultural traditions and values of different countries of the world, the effective use and management of international etiquette, ethical norms, integrated marketing communications. Business discourse is becoming increasingly popular as a topical area of research.

Discourse Overview I

The existence of discourse theory is increasingly felt in linguistics. Before moving directly to business discourse, let me briefly review the discourse. It should be noted that the development of the theory of discourse is related to the names of such scholars as E. Benveniste, U. Maas, M. Foucault, Z. Harris, E.S. Kubriakova, A. Kudlaeva, T. A. Van Dijk, N.D. Arutinova and many other scientists. The development of the theory of discourse in linguistics dates back to the 60s of the twentieth century.

Z. Harris, in his 1952 article entitled Discourse Analysis, explained discourse as a simple combination of phrases with continuous narration. The linguist of that era only considers language from a sentence level. Harris writes a broader analysis of language that does not dwell on the internal linguistic (sentence) level, but rather explores the connection between the text and the context.

U. Maas defines discourse as an appropriate linguistic formation in relation to socially and historically defined social practices [27, 204].

N. D. Arutinova defines discourse as speech, which is considered as a purposeful social action, as a component involved in the interaction of people and their mechanisms of consciousness, cognitive processes, this is speech "Hidden in Life" [1, p. 136-137].

T. A. Van Dijk defines discourse as a communication event that takes place between the speaker and the listener (observer, etc.), the process of communicative action takes place in the context of a certain time and space [8, 312].

There are various definitions of discourse in the linguistic literature. This is because discourse is a complex phenomenon: it is much more than a word, a sentence, a text, what is said. However, these are also components of discourse and without them there is no discourse.

V.I. Karasik distinguishes two main types of discourse: personal (person-centered) and institutional (status-oriented). In the first case the speaker appears as a person, with all his inner nature. In the second case - as a representative of a certain social institution (Karasik, 2000: 8). Participants in personal discourse know each other well, the speaker acts as an individual, while in institutional discourse he / she is "The communicative speech of the

representatives of social groups or institutions with each other, with people who are aware of the possibilities of their status-role. They have established a framework of social institutions, which is determined by the needs of society at a particular stage of its development "[4, p.280]. A key feature of institutional discourse is its involvement in social interaction, which takes place mainly within public institutions.

Institutional Discourse II

Institutional Discourse (English: Institutional Discourse, French: discours Institutionnel, German: Institutieller Diskurs) is communication in the established social institutions of society [T. A. Van Dijk, 2008].

In some linguistic works, the concept of "institutional discourse" is understood as "discourse produced in social institutions that involves communication as an integral part of their organization" [S Siegel, 2000, p. 43].

It is "specialized clichéd communication between people who may not have known each other personally, but should communicate in accordance with the regulations of that society" [Karasik, 2002, p. 292].

Any institutional discourse uses a certain system of professionally oriented signs or, in other words, has its own subtext (special vocabulary, phraseology) [24, 368]. A person enters a particular discourse space not only for a certain social role (including or implying the type of social institution), but also for certain purposes. Institutional discourse is a very broad concept that includes both the language system (the part of it that is specifically focused on a given section of communications), as well as speech activity (a combination of linguistic and extralinguistic factors) and text.

Institutional discourse is the communication of status-role relationships within a given framework [9, 14]. In modern society there are the following types of institutional discourse: political, diplomatic, administrative, legal, military, pedagogical, religious, mystical, medical, business, advertising, sports, scientific, scenic and mass information (mass media). Institutional discourse is distinguished by two systemic characteristics: goals and participants in communication [9, 15]. For example, the goal of political discourse is to seize and maintain power, pedagogical discourse is the socialization of a new member of society, business discourse is the establishment of mutually beneficial business relationships between organizations, and so on. The main participants in the institutional discourse are the representatives of a particular institution and the people who address them.

Thus, institutional communication is communication through a kind of mask [3, 66]. It is a stereotypical communication that fundamentally distinguishes institutional discourse from personal. The specifics of institutional discourse are revealed in its type, i.e. The type of public institution, which is defined by a special name in the collective linguistic consciousness, that is generalized in the basic concept of this institution (political discourse - power, pedagogical - teaching, religious - faith, legal - law, medical - health, etc.), It is related to certain functions of people, structures built to perform these functions, social rituals and stereotypes of behavior, as well as to the texts created in this social formation [5, 77].

Business discourse III

One of the interesting types and directions of institutional discourse is business discourse, which is characterized by institutional and cognitive-linguistic features and which distinguishes it from other types of discourse. This is to follow the rules of business communication. It manifests itself in defining the basic concepts of business culture, professionally managed ideas and concepts, norms of institutional and personal behavior.

According to A. Stebletsova, business discourse is a universal type of institutional discourse that provides the necessary level of communication interaction in any field of professional activity (Stebletsova, 2014).

According to Francesca Bargiela-Chiapini and Nickerson, Business discourse is verbal or written communication between people who are directly interested in business interactions to support their own interests (or the interests of their organization), while communicators are holders of specific status role relationships (Bargiela - Chiappini and Nickerson 2002).

It should be noted that business communication can be understood as any kind of communication between partners, which is aimed at resolving certain business issues and has an interpersonal character (Imametdinova 1996).

I find Shiriaeva's point of view quite interesting: He primarily understands business discourse as a person with purposeful verbal status and role activity; And business relationships, which are aimed at making a profit and are based on the rules and regulations adopted in the communication of the business community, which is their common feature (Shiriaeva 2014)

These definitions provide a visual representation of the status role (institutional) characteristics of business discourse, as well as its important quality, such as universality. Business discourse has been studied as a subtype of institutional discourse [5, p. 286];

For business discourse, not only special vocabulary is used, but also discursive formulas - special functionally defined speech flows that are characteristic of communication in a particular social institution (in this case, it is a business institution) [8, p. 10].

D. Naumenko, considers English-language business discourse as a kind of institutional discourse, which serves the professional community of business entities and clients, organized basic concepts BUSY (active, busy), ENTERPRISE (entrepreneurship), MANAGE (management), MARKET (market), PROFIT (profit), combined in the macro concept BUSINESS - business.

Business discourse basically includes two aspects that serve to establish communication for business purposes using different means in different contexts. The first is mentioned, as a spoken business discourse and reflected in business meetings, interviews, presentations, etc. And the second is known as written discourse and consists of emails, faxes, letters, business reports, and so on.

Institutional business discourse is a purposeful status role speech of people, which is a common feature of business relationships (production of goods, financing this production, issuance of cash loans, Insurance, trade, sales of products and various services, e.g. as goods registration, distribution and repair, purchase of goods or services, sale, preliminary negotiations on this type of business relationship), which includes not only internal organizations, but also communications between organizations as well as communication between organizations and individuals. Adherence to the norms and rules of communication is accepted in the business community [23.50].

Business etiquette IV

Ethics is an important part of communication culture. Thus, norms of behavior based on moral and ethical principles. There are various professional ethics available today. For example: journalism ethics, business ethics, doctor ethics and more. The key to modern business is successful negotiation and bargaining. In business communication, the interlocutors must follow the rules of business etiquette, otherwise the parties will not be able to reach an agreement. Rules of business etiquette are a combination of written and oral rules of conduct. We are taught the rules of behavior from childhood, these are more social rules of behavior. We have mastered them so that we can complete them automatically. By using the

same rules we can show respect to those around us. The rules of business etiquette are an extension of the same principles. Respect the people you have a relationship with at work.

It is the source of your success. Knowledge of business etiquette is essential for running a successful business. Knowledge of business etiquette can improve teamwork, relationship with partners, productivity and customer satisfaction.

Adherence to etiquette and ethics in business communication is a kind of "packaging" of a product called information. The better packaged the goods, the more attractive it is, therefore the more valuable it is. Within the communicating in business, when we want to reach some kind of agreement with someone each type of information needs to be conveyed as efficiently as possible, for which we need to use universally recognized norms of ethics and etiquette.

Institutional business relations - is the communication, It is the exchange of important information for the participants of the business relationship (between business entities). In order to achieve effective communication, it is necessary to clarify the following issues:

- What are the means of communication and how to use them properly in the process of business relations;
- How to overcome the barriers of misunderstanding and make communication successful.

The role and importance of communication in international business is great and it is constantly evolving.

The characteristics of business discourse institutionalization are:

- a specific purpose of communication;*
- specific participants;*
- a specific social chronotop;*
- specific values;*
- specific strategies;*
- a specific overall picture of the world;*
- specific characteristics of texts (Shiryaeva 2014).*

Features of formal business discourse include stability, standardization, because its field of application is business relations between people, institutions and states. Whereas official business discourse is characterized by strict accuracy, objectivity, specificity, conciseness, lack of imagery and emotionality; Then its choice of means is determined by the same characteristics. In particular, the use of international lexical items will not be dictated by a desire to implement a basic pragmatic attitude, as content expressed in a formal business style should exclude the possibility of ambiguity and inconsistency.

Conclusion

Thus, we can conclude that business discourse with "institutional universality", the purposefulness of speech behavior and the correlation of the business picture of the world, as a key parameter of interaction between communicators, has a clearly defined cultural and communicative orientation, as well as a characteristic pragmatic-semantic loading and stylistic regulation. Business discourse is a format of communication between individuals in which business relationships act as a common parameter; They are based on a common perception and understanding of the world business picture, a combination of professional values and knowledge, the most important principles of speech etiquette.

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ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ПАРАМЕТРОВ ПРЕССОВАНИЯ СЕМЯН БАХЧЕВЫХ КУЛЬТУР

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Аннотация: В статье рассмотрен процесс отжима масла из семян тыквы в шнековом маслопрессе, с применением метода планирования полнофакторного эксперимента. Для исследования взаимодействия различных факторов, влияющих на процесс отжима масла из семян тыквы, были применены математические методы планирования эксперимента. В качестве объекта исследования использовали семена тыквы (масличность 32 - 36 %).

Ключевые слова: прессование, семена тыквы, статистический анализ, масличность, математические методы планирования эксперимента

В связи с возрастающими объемами выращивания бахчевых культур в Казахстане, возникла необходимость создания эффективного технологического оборудования для переработки семян бахчевых культур. В Российской Федерации возрос объем выращивания штирийской тыквы в Краснодарском крае, семена которых после первичной обработки как масличное сырье отправляют на переработку в страны ЕС. Для разработки технологического оборудования требуются достоверные данные о физико-механических, аэродинамических и других свойствах, как семян тыквы, так и продуктов их переработки [1].

В семенах тыквы содержится ряд биологически активных веществ и витаминов, который может использоваться в медицине в лечебно- профилактических целях в виде масла и жмыха. Задача заключается в том, чтобы в вырабатываемых из семян масла и жмыхе содержались вышеуказанные вещества и витамины в натуральном виде.

Полезность и эффективность тыквенного масла, способы его получения изучаются учеными со всего мира. Множество трудов посвящено антиоксидантной способности тыквенного масла.

Регион Саярска в северо-восточной части Словении и на юге Австрии имеет давнюю традицию выращивания тыквы (*Cucurbita pepo* L., Cucurbitaceae) в качестве масляной культуры.

Масло семян используется для салатных соусов, но также используется в фармакологии и альтернативной медицине [2], особенно когда производится органически. Содержание масла в семенах тыквы колеблется от 40% до 50% в зависимости от генотипа. Масло темно-зеленое и содержит свободные жирные кислоты. Содержание витамина Е, особенно гамма-токоферола, очень велико [3].

Целью исследования Agnieszka Nawirska-Olszańska было определение антиоксидантных свойств и получение характеристик масла, полученного из семян 12 разновидностей тыкв, принадлежащих к виду *Cucurbita maxima* Duch. И *Cucurbita pepo* L. Другой задачей было установить, какой из двух экстрагирующих веществ, этанола или метанола, более эффективен. Получены следующие результаты:

Исследуемые семена тыквы отличаются химическим составом и антиоксидантной активностью.

- В семенах тыквы были идентифицированы только производные фенольных кислот в свободной форме.
- *С. Максимумы* семена характеризуются более высоким содержанием жирных кислот по сравнению с *С. Пено*.
- Антиоксидантная активность, полученная с 50% этанолом, была выше, чем у 80% метанола.
- Семена *С. maxima* характеризуются более высоким содержанием токоферолов[4].

Проведено экспериментальное исследование экспериментального исследования процесса получения масла из семян тыквы с помощью CO₂-экстракции. Проводится статистический анализ экспериментальных результатов; Статистическая и математическая модель процесса, определены рациональные параметры влияющих факторов [5].

Для производства растительных масел применяют прессовый способ, который включает следующие последовательные технологические операции – очистка семян от примесей, отделение оболочек, измельчение, тепловая (влажотепловая) обработка, прессование – остается практически неизменной на протяжении столетий. Однако использование альтернативных масличных культур предполагает уточнение оптимальных интервалов параметров прессования, для каждой конкретной культуры, с целью упрощения процесса в производственных условиях и снижения материальных и энергетических затрат [6].

Для сохранения всех ценных веществ в растительных маслах, полученных методом холодного прессования, необходимо правильно подобрать рациональные параметры для его извлечения [7].

Для исследования взаимодействия различных факторов, влияющих на процесс отжима масла из семян тыквы, были применены математические методы планирования эксперимента. В качестве объекта исследования использовали семена тыквы (масличность 32 - 36 %).

В качестве основных факторов, влияющих на процесс прессования, были выбраны: x_1 - начальная влажность сырья, %; x_2 - частота вращения шнека маслопресса, c^{-1} ; x_3 – величина зазора для выхода жмыха, мм; x_4 - температура мятки при отжиме, °C; x_5 – лузжистость исходного продукта, %.

Все эти факторы совместимы и некоррелируемы между собой. Пределы изменения исследуемых факторов приведены в табл. 1.

Таблица 1- Пределы изменения входных факторов

Условия планирования	Пределы изменения факторов				
	$x_1, \%$	x_2, c^{-1}	x_3	x_4	x_5
Основной уровень	10	0,8	0,5	80	6
Интервал варьирования	1	0,1	0,2	5	1
Верхний уровень	11	0,9	0,7	85	7
Нижний уровень	9	0,7	0,3	75	5
Верхняя "звездная точка"	12	1,0	0,9	90	8
Нижняя "звездная точка"	8	0,6	0	70	4

Выбор интервалов изменения факторов обусловлен технологическими условиями процесса прессования и техническими характеристиками маслопресса.

Критериями оценки влияния различных факторов на процесс прессования были выбраны: y_1 - удельные энергозатраты на процесс прессования, кДж/кг; y_2 – остаточная масличность жмыха, %; y_3 – комплексный органолептический показатель качества (КОПК).

Структура показателя качества рассматривается как совокупность основных органолептических свойств продукта и определяется как произведение дифференцированных (единичных) показателей по формуле:

$$y_3 = K_1 K_2 K_3 K_4 K_5, \quad (1)$$

где K_1 - вкус исследуемого продукта, K_2 - цвет исследуемого продукта, K_3 - запах исследуемого продукта, K_4 – внешний вид исследуемого продукта, K_5 – прозрачность исследуемого продукта.

Общая оценка получаемого продукта определялась как средний арифметический балл от оценок пяти независимых экспертов по столбальной шкале.

Для исследования было применено центральное композиционное ротатабельное униформпланирование и был выбран полный факторный эксперимент 2^{5-1} с дробной репликой $x_5 = x_1 x_2 x_3 x_4$. Порядок опытов рандомизировали посредством таблицы случайных чисел, что исключало влияние неконтролируемых параметров на результаты эксперимента.

$$y_1 = 0,132 - 0,039x_1 + 0,043x_2 - 0,078x_3 + 0,054x_4 + 0,019x_5 - 0,028x_1x_2 + 0,054x_1x_3 + 0,065x_1x_4 - 0,018x_1x_5 + 0,008x_2x_3 + 0,009x_2x_4 - 0,017x_2x_5 - 0,013x_3x_4 - 0,054x_3x_5 + 0,042x_4x_5 + 0,017x_1^2 - 0,017x_2^2 - 0,024x_3^2 + 0,066x_4^2 + 0,044x_5^2, \quad (2)$$

$$y_2 = 5,912 - 0,128x_1 + 0,184x_2 + 0,312x_3 - 0,390x_4 - 0,245x_5 - 0,344x_1x_2 - 0,026x_1x_3 + 0,041x_1x_4 + 0,584x_1x_5 - 0,223x_2x_3 + 0,675x_2x_4 - 0,159x_2x_5 + 0,146x_3x_4 + 0,148x_3x_5 - 0,266x_4x_5 - 0,083x_1^2 - 0,017x_2^2 + 0,135x_3^2 + 0,132x_4^2 + 0,165x_5^2, \quad (3)$$

$$y_3 = 9,365 + 0,037x_1 + 0,022x_2 + 0,386x_3 + 0,026x_4 + 0,018x_5 - 0,029x_1x_2 + 0,007x_1x_3 + 0,012x_1x_4 - 0,017x_1x_5 + 0,005x_2x_3 + 0,012x_2x_4 - 0,017x_2x_5 - 0,024x_3x_4 - 0,012x_3x_5 - 0,011x_4x_5 - 1,669x_1^2 - 1,456x_2^2 - 0,306x_3^2 - 1,032x_4^2 - 1,181x_5^2. \quad (4)$$

Задача оптимизации сформулирована следующим образом: найти такие режимы работы маслопресса, которые бы в широком диапазоне изменения входных параметров исходного сырья составляли минимум удельных энергозатрат, минимальную масличность жмыха и максимальный комплексный органолептический показатель качества. Общая математическая постановка задачи оптимизации представлена в виде следующей модели:

Введем предположение, что полученные уравнения регрессии (2) - (4) описывают некоторые поверхности в многомерном пространстве, а по коэффициентам канонической формы установим, к какому виду тел относятся эти поверхности.

В табл. 2 сведены выбранные оптимальные интервалы изменения параметров x_i для всех исследуемых выходных факторов.

Таблица 2 - Оптимальные интервалы параметров

у	$x_1, \%$		$x_2, \text{с}^{-1}$		$x_3,$		x_4		x_5	
	<i>min</i>	<i>max</i>	<i>min</i>	<i>max</i>	<i>min</i>	<i>max</i>	<i>min</i>	<i>max</i>	<i>min</i>	<i>max</i>
y_1	7,31	11,72	0,843	0,940	0,64	0,78	74	89	4,95	7,23
y_2	8,15	10,27	0,790	0,895	0,75	0,80	82	92	6,52	7,67
y_3	9,15	10,61	0,798	0,866	0,72	0,90	87	90	7,13	8,0

Согласно критерия оптимизации (5) для принятия окончательного решения по выбору оптимальных режимов исследуемого процесса необходимо решить компромиссную задачу, накладывая оптимальные, выделенные в табл. 3, интервалы параметров x_i друг на друга.

Таким интервалом для параметра x_1 - начальная влажность продукта оказался 9,10...10,23 %. Остальные независимые переменные: x_2 - частота вращения шнека, с^{-1} ; x_3 - величина зазора для выхода жмыха, мм; x_4 - температура мезги при отжиме, $^{\circ}\text{C}$; x_5 - лужистость исходного продукта, % конфликтуют между собой относительно критериев оптимизации.

Для проверки правильности полученных результатов был поставлен ряд параллельных экспериментов, полученные результаты попадали в рассчитанные доверительные интервалы по всем критериям качества. При этом среднеквадратичная ошибка не превышала 4,3 %.

Решение задачи с векторным критерием оптимизации осуществляется в два этапа - это выделение области компромиссов (решений, оптимальных по Парето) и дальнейшее ее сужение на основе некоторой схемы компромисса. Окончательный выбор решения осуществлялся исходя из физического смысла исследуемого процесса в области оптимальных значений выходных факторов.

В результате многофакторного статистического анализа процесса прессования можно сделать выводы:

1. Были получены регрессионные уравнения, анализ которых позволяет выделить факторы, наиболее влияющие на рассматриваемый процесс прессования масличных культур, на примере семян тыквы.

2. Впервые решена задача оптимизации нахождения диапазона изменения входных параметров исходного масличного сырья для получения максимального комплексного органолептического показателя качества.

3. В результате решения задачи с векторным критерием оптимизации были получены оптимальные интервалы входных параметров:

$$x_1 = 9,15...10,27 \%, x_2 = 0,843...0,895 \text{ с}^{-1}, x_3 = 0,750...0,800, x_4 = 87...89, x_5 = 7,13...7,23.$$

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ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECT IN "GREEN" LOGISTICS

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С каждым годом качество окружающей среды вызывает все большую обеспокоенность. Одной из самых актуальных проблем человечества является угроза безопасности цивилизации и окружающей среды, возрастание риска разрушения существующих экосистем. Обеспечение удовлетворения потребностей настоящего и будущих поколений, которое достигается, благодаря охране существующей экосистемы, сохранению экономического потенциала, расширению возможностей использования альтернативных источников энергии, **обеспечению жизни в здоровой естественной среде и** длительного развития за счет эффективного использования природных ресурсов – является основной целью экологической политики. Граждане имеют право жить в здоровой окружающей среде в соответствии с законодательством страны или в соответствии с такими международными соглашениями, как Всеобщая декларация прав человека. (1)

2010 год, объявленный по инициативе Президента Азербайджанской Республики «Годом экологии», дал толчок активизации осуществляемого комплекса мер по ООС и использованию природных ресурсов. В течение всего года активизировалось участие в создании новой, инновационной экономики и науки, учитывающих экологические особенности нового века, а также началась реализация мероприятий во имя длительного развития здоровой окружающей среды, учитывая их экономические и социальные интересы. Проводились мероприятия по: восстановлению загрязненных территорий, управлению отходами, расширению территорий зеленых насаждений «Зеленый марафон», в Азербайджане учрежден экологический альянс, создан первый на Южном Кавказе биосферный резерват и т.д., также созданы электронные ресурсы по специфическим областям, усилилась просветительская работа среди населения и т.д. Проводились выставки, целью которых являлось: собрать на одной площадке международные и местные компании, государственные и негосударственные организации, применяющие инновационные технологии в сфере охраны окружающей среды; установить связи сотрудничества и обменяться опытом.

За последние годы в Азербайджане в области ООС осуществлен ряд крупных инфраструктурных проектов. Повышенное внимание к «зеленому» аспекту логистических операций обусловлено повышением информированности потребителей, повышением спроса на специалистов по вопросам защиты окружающей среды, ростом важности факторов поддержания и защиты окружающей среды, а также растущим политическим воздействием и регулированием в этом направлении. Пытаясь уменьшить негативное воздействие и проявить заботу об окружающей среде родилась концепция «Зеленая логистика». Термин “зеленая логистика” означает методы управления цепями поставок и стратегии, которые снижают экологическое и ресурсное воздействие распределения потоков. Экологический аспект в логистической деятельности стал проявляться в рамках развития в экономической науке направления зеленой экономики, предполагающей, что экономика является зависимым компонентом природной среды, в пределах которой она существует и является ее частью, поэтому весьма разумно использовать термин «зеленая логистика».

Зеленую логистику можно определить как «производство и распространение товаров на устойчивой основе, с учетом экологических и социальных факторов общественного развития» [2]. Зеленая логистика включает все виды деятельности, связанные с экоэффективным управлением движения логистических потоков продукции, идущих от предприятия к потребителю, а также обратных потоков товаров, циркулирующих в системе «поставщик-потребитель» [3].

Исследователь Коблянская И.И. обозначает зеленую логистику как научно-практическую деятельность, которая направлена на учет экологических аспектов на всех стадиях движения материального и других сопутствующих ему потоков с целью оптимизации ресурсопотребления и минимизации деструктивных воздействий на окружающую среду [4]. В этом смысле зеленая логистика обеспечивает движение материала при осуществлении любых производственных процессов вплоть до его превращения в товар и отходы производства с последующим доведением отходов до утилизации или до безопасного хранения в окружающей среде, а также сбор и сортировку отходов потребления, их транспортировку, утилизацию или безопасное хранение в окружающей среде [5].

В настоящее время отрицательное воздействие логистических усилий проявляется в:

- ✓ наличии площади земель, занятых отвалами, накопителями, свалками отходов;
- ✓ загрязнении окружающей среды от переработки первичного сырья, "компенсирующего" неиспользование вторичных материальных ресурсов, содержащихся в отходах, а также тепла, содержащегося во вторичных энергетических ресурсах (ВЭР);
- ✓ выбросах в окружающую среду при производстве продукции из вторичных ресурсов (за счет исключения из технологической цепочки ряда звеньев);
- ✓ истощении и истощении прежней ресурсной базы при осуществлении логистических операций;
- ✓ строительстве объектов логистической инфраструктуры, которая сопровождается нарушением экосистем грунтовых вод;
- ✓ применении устаревших методов организации производственных процессов, которые способствуют загрязнению воздуха, воды, почвы, грунтовых вод вредными выбросами;
- ✓ применении транспортных средств, не соответствующих современным требованиям, оказывают опасные уровни шума и вибраций, создают дефицит нефтепродуктов, природного газа;

Следовательно, снижение экологической нагрузки на окружающую среду возможно только посредством экологизации всех ее функциональных областей. Важными экологическими проблемами в зеленой логистике являются потребление не возобновляемых природных ресурсов, а также удаление как опасных, так и неопасных отходов. Логистика обладает значительным потенциалом для осуществления экологического контроля транспортных систем, процессов утилизации продукции, упаковочных материалов, контроля и минимизации загрязнения, реализации процессов энерго- и ресурсосбережения, предоставляет возможность обеспечения экономической выгоды, защиты окружающей среды, улучшения репутации и имиджа компании и повышения конкурентоспособности на мировом рынке и социальной ответственности.

Опыт зарубежных стран позволяет констатировать, что применение ресурсосберегающих технологий в логистике позволяет сократить запасы материалов на 40-60 %, ускорить оборачиваемость оборотных средств на 20-40 % (основными

факторами которых являются: сокращение общей длительности технологического цикла; совершенствование технологии и организации производства; улучшение условий снабжения предприятий и сбыта продукции; чёткая организация платёжно-расчётных отношений); сократить транспортные расходы на 7-20 %, снизить расходы на погрузочно-разгрузочные и складские работы на 15-30 % [6].

Кроме того, во многих странах правовые нормы заставляют производителей и поставщиков отвечать возросшей ответственностью за товар после его продажи и в процессе оказания послепродажной сервисной поддержки [7]. С середины 90-х годов прошлого столетия именно поставщик или потребитель несет ответственность за возврат и ликвидацию упаковки, отходов и излишне произведенного продукта, а также за причиненный ущерб окружающей среде. Лидером является Германия, где на законодательном уровне (закон **Клауса Тёпфера** - немецкого политика и эксперта в области защиты окружающей среды, в 1998- 2006 г.г. занимал пост исполнительного директора Программы ООН по окружающей среде (ЮНЕП)) потребители обязаны возвращать всю упаковку розничному торговцу, розничный торговец - складу, а склад - производителю.

У логистических компаний есть много способов уменьшить вредное воздействие на окружающую среду, например, экологически чистый упаковочный материал, применяя материалы многократного использования, которые можно вернуть после выполнения перевозки, компания может реально сэкономить деньги:

- ✓ использование прочных и крепких поддонов, чтобы обеспечить долгосрочное использование;
- ✓ более эффективная упаковка предметов;
- ✓ упаковка предметов таким образом, чтобы их можно было разместить в одной коробке.

Чтобы сохранить органические продукты свежими и не навредить окружающей среде, ритейлеры по всему миру отказываются от пластиковой упаковки и переходят на биоразлагаемые (биodeградируемые) материалы. В связи с ухудшением в мире экологической обстановки термин «биоразлагаемые полимеры» стал неотъемлемой частью зеленого словаря, который означает способность материала разрушаться под воздействием окружающей среды и сохранять свои свойства только в период эксплуатации. Если емкости из нефтепродуктов разлагаются в течение нескольких сотен лет, то эко-упаковка распадается на безвредные составляющие за два-три года, разрушаясь как на воздухе (аэробное разложение), так и без участия кислорода — в почве или воде на компоненты, безвредные для живой и неживой природы: воду, углекислый газ, биомассу и др. Биоразложение полимерного материала может протекать только при наличии трех основных факторов: соответствующих условий окружающей среды, наличия микроорганизмов, селективно действующих на полимерный материал, и определенной химической структуры синтетического полимерного материала. В противном случае этот процесс как экологическая идея не реализуется. Значит радикальным решением проблемы загрязнения окружающей среды полимерным мусором (отходами синтетических материалов, используемых в качестве упаковочных и сельскохозяйственных пленок, изделий санитарно - гигиенического назначения и т.д.) может стать создание полимеров, способных подвергаться биodeградации (8-9). Например, в течение ближайших десятилетий европейским странам необходимо добиться 90 %-ной утилизации использованной упаковки по весу и 60 %-ной утилизации входящих в ее состав сырьевых материалов.

Таким образом, учет экологических норм поведения требует изменения традиционных подходов к управлению логистической деятельностью, переориентируя

предприятия на применение безопасных с точки зрения окружающей среды логистических технологий, уступая место зеленой логистике. Также, к сфере «зеленой» логистики можно отнести экологические проекты по строительству складов с использованием энергосберегающих технологий и экологически чистых строительных материалов; минимизацию затрат тепловой энергии при обеспечении сохранности и погрузке-разгрузке товаров; применение многооборотной тары и упаковки; повышение грузоподъемности транспортных средств; обеспечение утилизационных процессов в виде обратных цепей поставок (сбор и сортировка отходов, их доставка на распределительные склады, доставка готовой продукции, полученной из отходов, в торговую сеть и т.п.) [10].

Итак, зеленая логистика как научное направление, предполагает применение прогрессивных технологий логистики и современного оборудования с целью минимизации загрязнений и увеличения эффективности использования логистических ресурсов.

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NATURAL STRUCTURE AND FEATURES OF TOURIST AREAS OF THE MOUNTAINOUS ALTAI

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Annotation

The basis of modern rational natural resource management is scientifically-based territorial planning of the area, where a compromise between economic and ecological interests of man has been found. This approach is relevant to any field of human activity, including tourism and recreation.

Currently, tourism, both in Kazakhstan and Russia, is developing at a high rate. As a rule, it is timed to certain «landmark» areas of a country. One such area is Altai. However, tourism in Altai is very uneven and affects only a few key natural sites.

Intro

The mountainous Altai, covering the territory of four States, is a unique natural site. This is the highest region of Southern Siberia, with the height of alpine ridges more than 4000 m. Geologically, the territory of Altai is built by Proterozoic, Lower Paleozoic, Devonian and Paleogenic rocks [1]. Altai has a wide range of high-altitude explanations. The unique natural conditions of Altai provide a large number of endemic plants (*Campanula latifolia* L., *Rhodiola aigida*, *Astragalus roseus*, etc.) [2] and animals (snow leopard, black stork, golden eagle, etc.).

The general scenery of the mountains, the possibility of organizing different types of tourist routes, having different categories of difficulty (from the simplest 1 category to the most difficult 5 category) [3], attracts tourists from around the world, especially in the summer.

The aim of this work is to study the landscape features of tourist areas of the mountainous Altai and to identify their features within Kazakhstan and Russia.

Research Materials and Methods

To achieve this aim, literary sources and Internet resources were used, a landscape map of the studied area was built on the basis of which maps of landscape features of tourist areas of Altai and tourist routes in the study area were built. The ArcGIS program was used for mapping.

Results and discussion

1. Physical and geographical characteristics of the mountainous Altai

The mountainous Altai covers the territory of four States - the Russian Federation in the north, Kazakhstan in the south and south-west, Mongolia and China in the south-east. This natural site is unique - it is the highest region of Southern Siberia, and is a highly dismembered mountain relief with a height of mountain ranges of more than 4000 m (the highest point is the mountain Belukha with a height of 4509 m).

In geological terms, the territory of Altai is built by Proterozoic, Lower Paleozoic, Devonian and Paleogenic rocks. Highly metamorphized sericite chlorite slates, mica quartzites and amphiboles are the oldest of these. The process of folding the New Caledonian and Hercynian eras formed the main part of the tectonic structures of the Altai. The elevation amplitude is maximum in the central part and decreases at the periphery [4].

Altai belongs to the continental climatic belt. The air temperature decreases by 0.5° every 100 m. Thus, the average July temperature of the low foothills reaches 22°, while at an

altitude of 1000 m it drops to 16°. It is also necessary to take into account the temperature inversions inherent in the dismembered Altai relief, caused by the accumulation of cold air masses in the interstate basins. Moisture brought to the territory of Altai in the summer from the west and north-west, accumulates well, in this regard, the average mountain areas of the western part of the region (altitude of 1500-2000 m) receive up to 2000 mm of precipitation per year. However, it should be borne in mind that the interiors basins are particularly arid, so the Chu steppe has only 100 mm of precipitation. Most precipitation occurs in the autumn and summer.

In the territory of Altai, glaciers are widespread, the presence of which is due to the climatic conditions of the area. There are currently 1,500 glaciers, with a total area of more than 900 km². The largest glacier of the mountainous Altai - Big Taldurinsky with an area of more than 20 km².

Altai has a developed hydrographic network, which is an abundance of mountain rivers, the density of which reaches 800 km per 1000 km². The main part of the recharge is snow melt and summer rains. There are also many lakes of tectonic and moraine origin in the mountainous country.

The territory of Altai is divided into 3 natural zones - mountain-steppe, mountain-taiga and high mountain, and has a fairly wide spectrum of high-altitude explanation. From steppes in the south of the region to alpine meadows in the center of Altai. These unique natural conditions provide a large number of endemic plants (*Campanulatifolia* L., *Rhodiola* sp., *Astragalus* sp., etc.) and rare animals (snow leopard, black stork, golden eagle, etc.), many of which are listed in the red book [3].

The overall scenery of the mountains, the possibility of organizing different types of tourist routes, having a different category of difficulty (from the simplest 1 category to the most difficult 6 categories), attracts tourists from around the world, especially in the summer.

2. Landscape features of tourist areas of Altai

The first stage of work was the selection of tourist areas of Altai on the basis of their landscape features. Tourist areas were borrowed from «Encyclopedia of the tourist» (1993) [6]. The natural basis was the landscape map of the USSR by A.G. Isachenko (1988) [7].

Thus, the landscape map of Altai with the tourist districts of Altai was made (fig.1).

Figure 1. Map-diagram of tourist areas and landscapes of Altai
 Compiled by the author on the basis of the landscape map of the USSR A.G. Isachenko (1988) [6]

The tourist area of East Altai, covering the Shapshal ridge and the Chulyshman highlands, is a combination of sub-boreal typical Kazakh and Central Asian, as well as boreal Siberian and Far Eastern landscapes, having various geological structures. The highest point of Ak-oyuk is 3614 m (Shapshal Ridge). The main part of the tourist area occupies high mountain landscapes, the share of the middle mountain steppes is much smaller.

The steppes are represented by intramountainous depressions, folded-lump landscapes on Hercinian and Caledonian structures. Like the steppe landscapes, parts of the highlands also belong to the Hercinian and Caledonian epochs, but there are older pre-Cambrian landscapes. There are leveled denudation plains characteristic for these high mountain landscapes [6-7].

The main water artery of the district is the Chulyshman River, which flows into the Teletska Lake, however, in the territory of East Altai there is only the southern part of it. Surface run-off is the dominant form of river nutrition.

Vegetation in the Eastern Altai Mountains is a combination of herbal and leafy communities. The vegetation of East Altai is divided according to the high-altitude explanation. Here stands out the lower mountain-forest-steppe belt, where along with the steppe multigrass larch and birch forests with an abundance of shrubs, the mountain-forest belt is characterized by fir, cedar and fir forests, with height it is replaced by alpine meadow vegetation, The Nival Belt is represented by a few incrustated lichens. It is also worth noting the high proportion of endemic vegetation of the highlands (Mongolian-Sayan, Mongolian-Altai and Altai species) [7-8].

Steppe animal life is represented mainly by various species of rodents, birds, including predatory. The proportion of endemic steppe mammals is significant, at about 30%, but it is worth considering the total absence of taiga-zone endemics. On the territory of the reserve there is a large number of red book species: Altai mountain ram (fig.2), snow leopard, reindeer, etc. [3]

The degree of attractiveness of this tourist area is due to a number of unique natural objects. First of all, it is the Shapshal ridge with the category of complexity 1A-2B (low mountain areas requiring elementary mountaineering training), which is an attractive place for fans of mountaineering.

In general, it can be concluded that East Altai is quite stingy for the abundance of various natural landscapes, but still can be of tourist interest, and in various industries - from fishing to mountaineering. It is also worth noting the endemic flora and fauna, which has a positive impact on the tourist development of the area.

South-Eastern tourist area of Altai covers a large range of landscape zones - from semi-desert and steppe to high mountain. On the territory of the district are unique natural objects: Kurai and Chu steppes, surrounded by high mountain ranges of Chikhachev, as well as North Chui, South Chui and Kurai. It is worth noting the Ukok plateau, which is a relic of the mountainous Altai. The majority of the district occupy high mountain landscapes, the share of the middle mountain is much smaller, but there are unique for the region steppes. The highest point is Maashe-Bashi peak, reaching 4,177 m (North Chu Ridge).

The main part of the territory consists of Hercinian and Caledonian structures, but there are also older Paleozoic and Precambrian structures. The mountainous terrain is a deeply divided relief. The mountain ranges are made of sandstone, limestone and metamorphic rocks. Kurai and Chu basins, despite the high hypsometric level, are characterized by a high degree of aridity. The most arid areas of semi-desert and desert landscape zones are found in the Chu steppe [6-7].

The most important element of the hydrographic network of the tourist area is the Chuya River with its tributaries. On the other side of the Yuzhno-Chu range, the Argut River flows, which, like Chui, is a tributary of Katuni. Due to the flat surfaces of steppe landscapes, rivers on this site can meander, there is waterlogging. The main form of nutrition is surface run-off from nearby mountains. You can also highlight the abundance of small lakes, which is especially noticeable against the background of other tourist areas of Altai. This phenomenon is caused by active glacial activity.

In accordance with the high-altitude explanation, the vegetation of the South-East Altai changes. Here you can distinguish nivala belt. Below is the tundra-cryophynthesis belt, where along with the tundra vegetation there are areas with steppe grasslands and well-settled crayons and cobrers. This belt is replaced by a Head Rare with larch and cedar. The mountain-forest belt is represented by fir and cedar forests, mountain-steppe (on shallow soils) - small-dern-grassland. In the valleys of rivers there are Ivnyaks and toplevniks [7-8].

The main share of the animal world of Southeast Altai is represented by endemic species of rodents. Larger ungulate mammals as well as predators [3] are rare in mountainous areas.

Tourist interest in the area is a unique combination of landscapes. The completely carved parts of the steppes are in great contrast with the snow-capped peaks of the mountain ranges. It is worth noting the famous valley of Aktra (fig.3) with its abundance of beautiful glaciers. Also on the territory of this region is the famous Chuya River - a place of all-Union, and later international competitions in various water disciplines. The abundance of mountain ranges that provide climbing routes of varying complexity, not to mention the unique natural object - the Ukok plateau - has a great impact on the tourist development of this area.

The south-eastern region of Altai is quite attractive for tourism, as it provides all kinds of routes - from hiking and sightseeing to active water. However, the key point that distinguishes this area from the rest is the presence of an increased range of landscapes of different height and abundance of unique natural objects, as evidenced by the noticeably higher tourist load of the area.

Ore Altai, which is the smallest in area of tourist areas, is located inside the Central Altai and is a number of mid-mountain massifs. A small proportion of the highland landscape. The district covers the Ubinsky and Kolyvan ranges, as well as the spurs of Tigeretsky, Ivanovsky, Holzun and Ulbinsky Ranges. Tourism in Rudny Altai is not developed. A number of hotels near the city of Ridder offer a variety of leisure activities, including a few tourist routes. The highest point is Mount Linei Protein with a height of 2598 m (Ivanovo Ridge).

Unlike other tourist areas, the share of older pre-Cambrian and Paleozoic structures is much higher. High hilly and ridge-wet foothills located in the west of the district smoothly transition into typical steppe landscapes. High-mountain folding-block landscapes are found only in the southeast of the district [6-7].

The hydrographic network of South Altai is poorly developed. The most powerful rivers of the Black and White Uba, also worth mentioning is the Ulba River, which originates in the Ulbinsk Ridge (fig.4). The southern part of the tourist area is represented by a small number of low-power tributaries of the Irtysh.

The low mountains of the district are represented by a mountain-forest-steppe belt with birch-larch forests and grasslands with shrubs and flat meadows. The mountain-forest belt is predominantly with the larch taiga replaced by a sub-pastoral-sparse. Mosses and lichens predominate in the highland tundra belt. In the valleys of rivers there are Ivnyaks [7-8].

Wildlife is represented by a larger proportion of steppe species with a characteristic abundance of rodents, but in forest and forest steppe areas there are larger mammals, including predatory ones. It is worth noting the negative impact of human activities on natural habitats of animals [3].

Tourist Region Ore Altai is now a center of development of active recreation in the Kazakhstan part of Altai. But tourism has only recently developed here. Tours in this area are still the smallest and are sightseeing routes along the Ulbinsk ridge and its surrounding highlands.

North-Western tourist area of Altai, located between the rivers Charysh and Katuni, combines mainly forest low-mountain landscapes and mid-mountain steppes. There are also slight inclusions of high mountains. The region encompasses a number of small ridges - the Basilac, Seminsky, Anui, Cherginsky, as well as the eastern part of the Terekta ridge. The highest point with a height of 2,792 m is Uchemdek Mountain (Terektinsky Ridge).

The district is built by classical for Altai young Caledonian and Hercinian structures, with small inclusions of older Paleozoic. In general, the terrain is strongly partitioned, there is an active action of bulk processes. Abundance of rivers causes activity of alluvial transfer and accumulation of material [6-7].

The highly developed hydrographic network is due to the high dismemberment of the topography with the abundance of slopes that feed rivers with surface run-off. Most of the rivers are tributaries of Obi and Katuni. The most powerful of them are Anui, Sandstone and Sema. There is little waterlogging in the wetlands.

The vegetation of the North-Western Altai, in particular its southern part is represented by variegated grasses and grasses steppes. The vegetation of the low-mountain-steppe belt depends on the exposure of the slopes. The southern slopes are occupied by shrub-grassland-multi-herb-steppe vegetation, while the northern - meadow-steppe. With the increase of height on the northern slopes, grassland steppes are replaced by deciduous fir forests at lower altitudes than on the slopes of the southern exposition [7-8].

The highlands are predominantly alpine and subalpine vegetation, with little tundra and woodlands.

Low forest cover affects the fauna of the region, represented by small mammals of low and medium elevations, and larger, high-altitude landscapes. There are many rodents and birds [3].

North-Western Altai has good trails along the river valleys, which creates favorable conditions for beginners. There are also routes of increased complexity, especially in the area of the Terekta Ridge.

Thus, it can be concluded that North-Western Altai is one of the most convenient tourist areas, combining various types of routes, including a unique for the Altai speleo-tour (Denisova cave (figure.5)), and levels of difficulty (from 1 to 5 k.s.). It also contributes to the development of infrastructure and scenic local terrain, which favorably distinguish this area from others.

North-East Altai is represented mainly by middle and high mountain landscapes and covers the territory from the Katuni River in the west and up to the Biya River in the east. On the territory of the district there are ranges Jolong and Sumaltinsky, as well as the most important water object - Teletskoye Lake. The highest point of the North-East Altai with a height of 2756 m belongs to the Sumaltinsky ridge.

The area is heavily divided, but gradually recovers to the north, moving from high mountain landscapes to lowland forest steppe. The northern part is poorly drained, due to the predominance of flat plains with characteristic suffosion west and troughness. The southern

part of North-East Altai is Hercinian and Caledonian, but in the north there are more denuded Paleozoic terrain [6-7].

The hydrographic network of the district is represented by the powerful Katun River and its tributaries. The northern part is heavily swamped, due to the characteristics of the local landscapes. Teletsk Lake is the largest in the territory of not only the North-Eastern District, but also the entire Altai and is actively used in tourist activities. In the east of the district flows the Chulyshman River, also of interest to tourists who love rafting.

Almost all ridges of this area have a submeridian extension. In the mountain-forest belts there is a predominance of aspen-fir forests with high-grass meadows, in the foothills surrounding the Teletsk lake - cedar-larch forests. There are also birch-aspen secondary forests, high-altitude levels are occupied by alpine meadows.

Low-mountain landscapes are represented by a mountain-forest-steppe belt with birch-larch forests and dry shrub steppes and a mountain-forest belt of larch, cedar and fir forests. The middle mountains are characterized by the distribution of cedar-fir and deciduous-cedar-fir-fir forests. The highlands are represented by the tundra belt. River floodplains are often occupied by marshy birch and spruce-birch forests[7-8].

Teletsky Lake has a rich species composition of fish, including unique ones (Teletsky sig). There are also species of mammals endemic to Altai (Altai mole, Altai pike, etc.) [3].

North-East Altai is the most developed tourist area, which is still actively used. The advantageous location of settlements and well-developed paths contribute to its development in general. The most attractive routes along the foothills surrounding the Teletsk Lake (fig.), there are also water tours. The attractions include the Karakol Lakes, the caves of the Jolong Range and the Taldinsky Massif.

Tourist area of North-East Altai is one of the most developed tourist areas. Nearby settlements are the starting point for many tourist routes, which has a positive impact on the tourist development of the area as a whole.

Tourist area - South Altai is located on the territory of Kazakhstan and is a much more prominent arid plain landscape with little participation of mountain massifs in the eastern part. The famous Lake Markakol, the Buchtar Reservoir and the Tarbagatai Range are among the key features of the area. The highest point is the Berkutaul Mountain with a height of 3,773 m (Sarymsakty Range).

The young Hercinian and Caledonian structures of South Altai occupy a small area of the tourist area, the share of the Podgorod alluvial and proluvial plains. The local mid-mountain ranges are composed mainly of dense metamorphized rocks and granites.

The most powerful hydrological artery of the region is the Buchtarma River, which penetrates the mountain ranges of Southern Altai and flows into the Buchtar reservoir. To the west, the Irtysh River flows, which also flows into the Buchtar reservoir. In general, the hydrographic network is scarce and represents an abundance of temporary watercourses and a number of underdeveloped tributaries of Buchtarma and Irtysh. The number of lakes is minimal due to predominantly flat terrain [6-7].

In the interorne basins of the region there are wormwood-grain steppes. The foothills are occupied by a mountain-steppe belt with dry steppe fine-turf-grain vegetation. The mountain-forest-steppe belt of the low mountains is represented by birch-larch forests with inclusions of wormwood-grass steppes. The low-mountain mountain forest belt is represented by subtracted deciduous forests with a mixture of pine and larch. The middle mountain belt is characterized by rare-leaf fir forests. The higher points are the alpine meadows, which are gradually moving into the high tundra belt with moss-lichen vegetation [7-8].

In the rivers and lakes of South Altai there are many endemic species of fish: Uskuch, Lenok, Charius and Piscium (Lake Markakol). The area is also rich in bird and mammal species, including endemic steppe and mountain [3].

In the territory of South Altai there are no picturesque highland landscapes and, as a result, mountain rivers - the objects are the most attractive for active tourism, as a result, tourist routes here have received minimal development

South Altai does not provide active tourist routes, specializing mainly in health recreation. The favourite tourist sites include Lake Markakol, as well as the Buchtar Reservoir and the Rahman Keys. It is also worth noting the endemicity not only of steppe, but also of mountain animals and vegetation, and the abundance of water bodies actively used for fishing [3].

Central Altai covers the largest territory and the most inaccessible mountains. Here, both low-altitude landscapes and high-altitude (Katuny ridge, spurs of the Yuzhno-Chuy and Terekta ranges) were formed. Belukha Mountain (fig. 8) with a height of 4506 m is the highest point not only of the Central Altai, but also of the Altai mountain country as a whole.

The western part of the Central Altai is noticeably lower, it gradually passes into the eastern high mountain. The geological structure of the area, as well as most of Altai, refers to the Caledonian and Hercynian epochs of mountain formation. Older structures are prone to denudation. There are tundra, glacial alpine and subalpine meadow landscapes [6-7].

The hydrological network covers part of Katuni and Charysh, with their numerous mountain tributaries. Waterlogging is insignificant due to the strong division of the area. Rivers are fed by abundant surface run-off from adjacent mountain ranges.

Dry wormwood-grassland steppe vegetation with karagana formed in interorne basins.

The low mountains of Central Altai are represented by mountain-forest-steppe (larch-birch forests with shrub steppes) and mountain-forest (birch-aspen bush-high-grass forests) high-rise belts. The middle mountains are characterized by cedar-fir-coniferous forests, which are replaced by alpine meadows. The highlands are occupied by tundra vegetation [7-8].

Wildlife is richest in large mammals compared to other tourist areas, which is typical of mountain and forest areas. Rodents predominate in the open steppe spaces. Rare red book species (snow leopard, black stork, golden eagle, etc.) [3] are marked on the territory of Katunsky Reserve.

Central Altai provides tourists with the most complex climbing, which is a feature of the area (the presence of the highest mountain ranges and Belukhi mountains). There is also a wide range of water, automobile and foot sightseeing routes. It is worth noting the large number of protected areas that also make adjustments to tours.

Conclusions

The selected tourist areas of Altai Mountain have a unique combination of landscape features that significantly distinguish them from each other. The differences are represented not only by relief systems of different complexity, but also by the aggregate of biogeocenoses of each district.

On the basis of the above, it can be concluded that each of the regions can represent a unique range of types of tourist routes. So for example, the North-Eastern tourist area, thanks to the presence on its territory of the powerful mountain river Katun, can provide a large number of alloys, while the Central tourist area, on the territory of which is the highest point of the Altai mountain country - Belukha mountain, ideal for hiking.

The revealed specification will allow the most rational to reveal the tourist potential of Mountain Altai as a whole, developing the most convenient types of routes of each district.

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NEW MEDIA DEVELOPMENT TRENDS IN KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract. The article tells about the innovations and the effectiveness of new media in the information space, based on some topical issues in the history of Kazakhstan journalism. The competitiveness of Kazakhstani journalism in the use of new media and features of facts and narration, a system of genres and the process of transformation in the media are considered. The influence of world trends in journalism on the Kazakhstani media and information dissemination activities is described. Along with the capabilities of the new media, the problems of threats are analyzed, scientific conclusions and specific recommendations are made.

In the article, the authors study current trends in the development of media in Kazakhstan. Information is also provided on the implementation of the state program “Digital Kazakhstan” in Kazakhstan and a concept aimed at improving the competitiveness of the media. This data will discuss the government’s plan to develop new media, including the Internet, and today’s results. The article provides a comparative analysis of the speed of the Internet, the formation of new media in Kazakhstan, development paths, various ways of providing information, issues of determining and rating the rating of information sites, information security, media literacy.

Keywords: media, digital technology, infographics, national journalism, internet, convergence, information security, media literacy, fact-finding

1. Introduction. The transition of the media to digital broadcasting has raised the status of the distribution and reception of information to a new level. The main source of communication is the Internet in Web 3.0. The main distinguishing features of the new media are interactivity and digital dissemination of data. This broadcast format has opened up new possibilities: the creation of forms such as video, graphics and interactive, as well as the publication of materials using multimedia content. The development of new media has radically changed the work of journalists, dividing them into such social groups as the audience and sources of information, and relations with journalistic organizations and journalists have acquired a new character.

New media occupy a special place in the development trends of traditional journalism. After all, the dissemination of information, the narration of facts and events in the past was completely different. The range of media capabilities has increased. Information is presented not only in text but also in various multimedia versions. The form of communication with the audience has changed much faster and more efficiently than before. Speaking about the possibilities of new media, it is necessary to mention the Internet, which influenced it. We

have reached infinity of information thanks to the penetration of the Internet into our lives. Today you can read news on various topics from different sites, forums, blogs. The Internet has had a significant impact on the transformation of journalism. It is no exaggeration to say that citizen journalism, convergent journalism, blog journalism, online journalism, and multimedia journalism are rapidly developing in new media.

Most importantly, an archive of newspapers, magazines, television and radio programs has become available. Another feature is that new media influence the development of democratic processes. During the years of independence, the media, which were previously censored under the influence of the Soviet authorities, began to appear with a new character and new content. There is the possibility of freedom of speech and freedom of speech. They can conduct research on social and economic issues and prepare reports on various topics. There were also skills and abilities to work live. Along with such news, there are dangers. In particular, information security has become a global issue. We also understand that we still need to improve our knowledge of fact-checking and media literacy.

New media have a significant impact on traditional media. First, the economy of periodicals plummeted. Media competition is growing every day. Various methods of communication with the audience are used in accordance with the requirements of the information market. On the contrary, we cannot rule out shortcomings, such as the struggle to maintain the rating, the publication of false information without verification, the fabrication of various rumors. Secondly, although the channel switched to digital technology, it became dependent on cheap or talk shows. Some independent television channels spend most of their airtime on cheap overseas television shows. Thirdly, the development of new media poses new challenges for the media. Coordination of traditional and web editing services, opening several accounts on social networks, sending a new release of a publication or sorting information by e-mail, preparing a mobile version of multimedia, connecting to the Internet, presenting or formatting your material, etc. methods are used.

In the article we focus on the following issues of determining the development trends of new media in Kazakhstan. First of all, we will focus on Kazakhstani programs related to the availability of digital technologies, the quality of electronic services and improving the competitiveness of the media. The answer to the question of what are the results and effectiveness of the concept of increasing the competitiveness of the media of the Ministry of Information and Social Development of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Secondly, we study the impact of new media on traditional media. Are you satisfied with the current state of traditional media and their achievements? Thirdly, the analysis of ways to identify fake information on information sites and portals. When developing new media, we decided to focus on editorial management and marketing. In short, the audience began to use the media in accordance with their interests and needs. As a result, the editors established close ties with the audience. According to scientists, speaking about the media, one should not forget about the first two problems - about different levels of the audience, and the second - about different forms of dissemination of information. In other words, convergent journalism not only opened up new opportunities for professionals, but also turned them into a source of income. Based on this, the following question or question is determined. What methods are used to determine the rating among the media? Are you satisfied with the capabilities of the technology used by the rating company?

In truth, today humanity is a victim and even a fan of the online system. Because it spreads quickly and on time. In particular, online broadcasting negatively affects the viability of the newspaper. It is better to read the electronic version than to buy a newspaper. "Why pay for a free world?" The ideology of the old adage was a heavy blow to the press. The most effective way today is a process that does not require you to wait for your favorite message in

front of the TV and computer. You can watch the latest events and shows anytime, anywhere using your mobile phone. Also, if we look at the statistics for the last 5 years, reading news on social networks has become a trend that has increased several times. It should be noted that information is provided not only by journalists, but also by users of social networks. However, the flow of information on the Internet is a great opportunity for a journalist. Sometimes reporters and presenters can sit in one place and create a story. But this is not often the case. On the contrary, when there is a crisis and various obstacles, we turn to the traditional media. In this case, real journalists can identify and study information. This is a great advantage. When considering the term “media”, two things must be taken into account. The first is audience diversity. For example, gender and race, compatibility with various factors, and the second is the presence of many forms in the media. That is, as mentioned above, this is the development of convergence [1, p. 23].

Various multimedia and interactive approaches to disseminating information have also transformed traditional genres. In this regard, new media had a significant impact on the system of genres. The analysis of specific examples is based on the findings of scientists related to the integration and transformation of journalism genres. For example, when preparing material in analytical genres, a journalist can show many arguments with the help of pictures, videos and present only the main conclusions. The dialogue genre has also become the most active genre. Reporting can be done by any network user. However, professional reporting uses different approaches. He sought to present information on television in various forms using digital technology. In this regard, it should be noted the program of the TV channel "Qazaqstan".

2. Literature review. Returning to history, before Kazakhstan gained independence, the media were subjected to strict censorship. It was impossible to raise national issues in Kazakh-language publications and on television. However, the national intelligentsia published newspapers and magazines in a democratic direction, in which they published articles on the freedom and liberty of the Kazakh people. Therefore, the Alash press in the history of journalism can be represented as a brand in the modern media space.

In this regard, we would like to focus on the ideas expressed in the published article. «The Kazakh national journalism from the moment of its origination and up to the present moment has gone through a long and complicated way, having experienced as the Kazakh nation in general the pressure of the Tsarist Russia government, the pressure of the Soviet totalitarian state and achieved certain success and educated a n entire galaxy of remarkable journalists and publicists contributed to the development of national conscience and self-identity of the Kazakh people.

The Kazakh print media raised the issues of national development, pointed out at the obstacles towards it, tried to withstand to the exaggerations in implementation of the plans of national policy of the communist party. Simultaneously there was a process of covering the issues of development of culture, art and literature of the Kazakh people.

The best representatives of the Kazakh intelligentsia contributed by their speeches published in the press to the achievement of the factual equality of the Kazakh people with the other peoples of the USSR, but they spoke against smoothing national differences, withstood to the process of artificial formation of a new international community – the Soviet nation. The fight for the national interests contradicted to the plans of the administrative command system and thus was negatively assessed by it.

Despite the fact that the journalists and publicists, writers and poets were labeled as nationalists, were exposed to repressions and were sometimes even physically liquidated, the Kazakh national journalism stood for the true friendship between the people, raised in the

audience the sense of gratitude for the rendered assistance and formed in it readiness to help other nations living beyond Kazakhstan» [2].

The potential of Kazakh journalism during the years of independence began to develop rapidly in a new character, in a new content. Of course, we cannot hide the influence of the new media. In this regard, we should keep in mind two issues when considering the term media. The first is that the audience is at different levels [p. 3.19]. For example, gender and race, suitability for various factors, etc. The second is that there are many forms in the media. That is, the development of convergence.

The history and experience of journalism, industry journalism, as well as a number of studies of domestic scientists related to new media are currently used in higher education. In particular, N.B.Eskuatova, G.S.Sultanbaeva's "Internet Journalism" (2015), G.S.Sultanbaeva, A.B.Alimzhanova's "Multimedia Journalism" (2016), A.B.Alimzhanova's "Blog Journalism" (2016), S.Kh.Barlybaeva, A.B.Alzhanova, K.N.Myssayeva "Convergent journalism" (2016) textbooks were used in elective disciplines. There is also a lot of research on new media.

Research on the formation and development of online journalism has not yet been completed. We already know that several textbooks on the Internet have been published. Among them are E.Myrzabekov, A.Sh.Kulmuratova, L.K.Smailova, L.K.Tazhibay "Internet technology", B.Buribayev, G.A.Madiyarova "Web-technologies" explains the history, activities, programs and methods of working on the Internet, recommended by the Scientific Council of the Kazakh Agro Technical University named after S.Seifullin. The scientific article of Doctor of Philology, Professor N.Omashev "Globalization, national interests and journalism", Candidate of Philological Sciences, Associate Professor A.Beisenkulov's "Kazakhstan mass Problems of development of mass media on the basis of new technologies", scientific articles of A.Ramazan, candidate of philological sciences "Adaptation of mass media in Kazakhstan to the conditions of globalization" provide only an overview of the development of online journalism. In these works, we could not find an accurate reference to online newspapers.

Russian scientists A.A.Kalmykov, L.A.Kokhanova, V.N.Monakhov have written a number of research papers on the formation and development of Internet journalism. These studies are based on data and information from the Russian media. However, some information about the history and practice of Internet journalism, comments on the description of online newspapers, sites, portals were used in the work.

A.Erkimbay's research "New media: from monologue to dialogue", E.Kapkyzy and K.Mysaeva's research "Journalistic education today: innovations, new technologies" in connection with the new Kazakh language media also became the basis for scientific conclusions in the article.

Convergence is a term that covers different areas. We say that a journalist is versatile and understands the essence of any field. He created quality journalism by interacting with people who are ready to provide philanthropic help to those in need. Not only the rich, but also ordinary people help quality journalism. A journalist can convey open views by linking to information. Unlike before, now the audience can determine how educated and open-minded. For example, while the number of periodicals has increased in China and India, Russia and Japan, in Europe, on the contrary, the online platform is being used systematically. According to them, this is the future.

In any part of the world, traditional media and new media go hand in hand. Perhaps such a balance is appropriate. Because if everyone switched to modern trends, it would be of little use. The role of online journalism in the new era of the press is very important. Modern journalists have the opportunity to exert personal influence. This opportunity can cover the world, the whole continent. The power of the Internet is the same. No other media outlet can

conquer the world like the Internet. For example, Uzbekistan does not read Kazakhstan's newspapers and Europe does not listen to Russian radio. No one can demand it. And Internet sites can be translated from language to language and read by anyone on a smartphone. Without one of the networks, such as Google, Yandex, Opera, Youtube, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, there is probably no one who does not use one.

Another feature of media journalism is that it does not depend on anyone's investment. He is able to earn money and be self-sufficient for the review of each material and the number of points (likes). A new form of modern media is a dynamic dialogue [4, p. 42]. Whatever he says, the journalist will be in direct contact with the people. You can find out his opinion during the live broadcast and in the comments under each material on the network. Accordingly, it accepts daily errors and requests from viewers. In many cases, a journalist can identify the idea or problem of his next new work by communicating with his readers on his social network page. For example, during the pandemic, many journalists broadcast live on their pages with celebrities and audiences on various topics and discussed current issues.

In the new century, the world of the Internet, fully equipped in accordance with the global digitalization, has become a multi-platform platform for learning and learning. While there are downsides to this, quality content is struggling with them. The novelty of the century is to see the whole essence of our time on a smartphone like a mirror in your hand.

Currently, Kazakhstan has adopted special legislation aimed at creating an e-government. As before, there is a long queue and you can order any service at home without waiting. Moreover, it is expected to prevent communication and corruption.

The concept of e-government in public policy in the development of the information space, covering a wide range of society and business, is implemented in several programs. For example, a program for the formation and development of the national information infrastructure for 2001-2003, an e-government strategy in 2004, opportunities for the formation of this strategy in 2005-2007, and a development program for 2008-2010 were developed. And this idea is an important part of increasing national competitiveness, especially the use of information technology in public administration.

In accordance with the strategic development program of the state, it is planned to increase competitiveness in all areas, to reach a level where it can stand shoulder to shoulder with civilized countries. At the same time, the burden on the media is not small. The most important thing is the development of new media. In this regard, the concept of increasing the competitiveness of the media in Kazakhstan has been adopted several times. In particular, the Concept for the Development of Competitiveness in the Information Space of the Republic of Kazakhstan was adopted in 2006. The Concept of Competitiveness Development for 2006-2009 defines the basic principles. In 2011, the Concept of Information Security of the Republic of Kazakhstan until 2016 was adopted.

On behalf of the President of Kazakhstan Kassym-Zhomart Tokayev, a national strategic plan for the development of the information industry for 2020-2023 was developed. The Minister of Information and Social Development D. Abayev made the following statement in connection with the concept of competitiveness in the field of information. "Within the framework of the document, work will be done on the competitiveness of the Kazakh media. Many measures are being developed now. But now we can talk about their limits. First, we implement the state information policy. For this purpose, the mechanisms of the state information order will be reconsidered. When we introduce market prices, we focus on quality, not quantity. The state supports the distribution of multimedia content in demand among the population on the Internet, rather than its published number. Secondly, we are ready to support commercial TV channels and radio stations to find their way in digital broadcasting. " In addition, the Minister said that in 2021 a system for media evaluation of the

audiences of TV channels and Internet resources will be developed in the implementation of the state policy order. "Fourth, regulations will be developed to regulate Internet TV channels. Last year, the Ministry prepared a project to optimize media legislation and access to information. There are many action plans. Among them is the zero value added tax for paper publications "[5], - said D. Abayev.

The issue of full provision of broadband Internet to increase competitiveness in the media sector is one of the issues that the Government of Kazakhstan is not paying attention to. On December 12, 2017, the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan approved the state program "Digital Kazakhstan". The main goal of the program is to accelerate the development of the country's economy in the medium term and improve the quality of life through the use of digital technologies, as well as to facilitate the long-term transition of Kazakhstan's economy to a radically new development trajectory. The main objectives of the program are the gradual digitization of the entire industry, increasing the number of smart cities and smart villages.

The only mechanism for implementing the "Digital Kazakhstan" program is the availability of the Internet. Unfortunately, during the global pandemic, the program's shortcomings became apparent. It was found that the speed of the Internet is very low, even in large cities, except for remote villages, which are not provided with broadband Internet. We noticed it during distance learning. For the implementation of the Program in 2018-2022, the budget provides funds in the amount of 108,683,142 thousand tenge [6].

"Currently, broadband Internet is available in 117 cities and 3,324 rural areas of the country. In 2018, Kazakhstan ranked 21st in the world in terms of mobile subscribers. The number of Internet users in Kazakhstan in 2018 was 81.3% and Kazakhstan ranked 45th in the world rankings.

It is planned to build fiber-optic and LTE (4G) networks in 2018-2021 to further cover rural areas with broadband Internet. In addition, a new generation of 5G communication is developing in parallel to provide broadband wireless connectivity, Internet of Things and high-speed technologies. Currently, 5G tests are being conducted in Nur-Sultan and Almaty, which are scheduled for October this year in Shymkent.

Thus, as a result of the work done, by the end of 2022, 97% of rural areas will be covered by broadband Internet "[7]. The issues discussed at the meeting of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan were not left out during the pandemic. At the meeting of the National Commission, the Government has repeatedly discussed specific plans and measures to provide broadband Internet.

3.Methodology. Evolutionary development has made it possible for everyone to achieve success and offer many opportunities. First of all, let's talk about the advantages of the media. The first opportunities were the emergence of television and radio. This made it possible for people in remote areas to receive messages. The population has been educated, the work of media professionals has been halved. These changes have been implemented since 2010 and have achieved a lot in the ten years since then. The user audience has also expanded and the ratings have started to rise.

Information sites, national Internet newspapers, bloggers, social networks are rapidly developing in order to achieve high efficiency of information exchange using the rich potential of the Internet. According to statistics, Kazakhstan was one of the first CIS countries to develop the Internet, adopted a special program and allocated funds from the state budget. Therefore, we see that only the media itself is interested in the formation of the Kazakhstan segment of the Internet. It is known that even special funds have invested heavily in the implementation of this policy of the state. To prove our point, the Presidential Foundation for the Development of the State Language published the following information on its website on

February 10, 2010: b]. Today, due to the fact that the share of the Kazakh language in the world Internet is only 3%, it is important to open Kazakh-language websites in various areas.

We understand that the media and the media do not mean the same thing. Concepts such as newspapers, magazines, television, which belong to the media, are included in the media. But the media is a broad concept in itself. The letter covers everything from a picture engraved on a stone to information exchange. Depending on the form of the media, changes in society can be observed. Because the media and society are inseparable. The development and transformation of the media depends on changes in society. The development of technological devices such as computers has given rise to the phenomenon of new media.

Today, the society is dependent on the development of new media opportunities, the Internet. In other words, the Kazakh reader is not able to accept any information and products provided by the Internet in the same way and influence it from his own side. From this point of view, we still need to be literate in our understanding of the new media, our view of the Internet. Experts in the field of the Internet, scientists and public figures also speak about it.

When it comes to new media, terms related to the Internet are often heard. Journalists also use phrases such as "digitalization" and "online newspaper." In this regard, we would like to pay attention to the opinion of A. Erkimbay on the differences between digital media, online media and new media.

"Digital media is a digital form of all information. This type of anti-digital media is called "analog media". In analog media, data is also encoded in numbers, but stored in a physical object. For example, on magnetic tape, on paper. The letters on the pages of the book do not change after printing. We can't change the music recorded on plastic tape. The four main features of digital media are:

First, the text is not tied to a specific media. For example, in the past, all texts (words, pictures, music) were available only on paper, but today we can read the text on a monitor, pocket phone or e-booklet, download images from the Internet and browse digitally.

Second, we can compress information into smaller volumes. You can also store entire libraries on USB flash drives. For example, 1 gigabyte is equivalent to 4,500 200-page books.

Third, any information in digital media is easy to find and manage. For example, if you need information from hundreds of books on your flash drive, you will find the information you need in one breath without having to turn the pages of the book.

Fourth, you can change the information. For example, you can change the color of an image to make it unrecognizable with the click of a button or two. We realized that digital media is primarily about technological features.

The online media phrase applies primarily to the Internet. The main feature of online media is the closeness of the distance in the exchange of information. But the distance between which information is exchanged cannot be the main feature of the media. Improved the quality of remote information exchange in online media. If we say that digital media is replacing analog media, we cannot say that online media is the main one. The type of online media includes media content distributed through mobile phones. Such media is thus applied to the concept of distance, which is an important feature of media.

New media is a phenomenon that combines the computational methods of the computer and the communicative capabilities of the media. The new media term also includes the above digital and online features. This is the secret of using the Internet as a new media, even though it has been around for almost 40 years. New media is not only the Internet, but also new opportunities and ways of communication and information exchange, which are developing on the basis of technological processes "[p. 8,10].

Scientists are still studying new media as new. The reason is directly related to the capabilities of the media. With the help of technology, consumers of traditional media can

listen to videos of news, newspapers, and radio broadcasts that they cannot see anywhere on their mobile phones. New media brings together all types of traditional media and gives us a lot of opportunities. In addition, scholars have viewed the relationship between the editor and the reader as direct and inverse. For example, through the chain of journalism - text - audience, B. Zhakyp [9, 12] shows the connection between the creator and receiver of the media. In the new media, this connection is two-way. That is, the recipient of information can become a transmitter at any time. If a certain editorial office publishes an article on the website, the Internet user can read it, add their opinion and then share it with their friends on social networks.

Consumption of Internet services is not widespread. Often programmers, representatives of large businesses became the first active users of the Internet in Kazakhstan.

The development of new media in Kazakhstan has been directly influenced by three different groups: the government, commercial structures, and non-governmental organizations. The authorities have enacted a law defining the main official position on the Internet in Kazakhstan. According to the law adopted in Kazakhstan, all Internet resources are equal to the media. Kazakhstan's media, which emerged from a semi-closed Soviet system, had to overcome two main obstacles to become part of the global media system. The first is the adaptation to market conditions, ie most newspapers and magazines accustomed to public funding have limited ability to compete. The second is to eliminate technological backwardness. Only those who were able to overcome these obstacles were able to survive in the context of globalization.

"The adaptation of the media in Kazakhstan to globalization has gone through several stages. In the first stage, in 1986-1991, as a result of the reconstruction in Kazakhstan, the prestige of the media increased, and many innovations were introduced in terms of content and information. At the same time, the media, which could not go beyond one ideology in a totalitarian society, gradually entered the market situation, making effective use of publicity. Reconstruction and publicity not only increased the political role of newspapers and magazines in society, but also increased their circulation.

The 1990 Law on the Press allowed individuals to publish newspapers. As a result, in the early 1990s, newspaper and magazine groups began to privatize their publications.

The second stage covers the period from 1991 to 1998. During this period, Kazakhstan has seen a rapid growth of the media. At the same time, competition between periodicals and electronic media has intensified. According to some sources, in 1997 there were about 40 TV channels in Kazakhstan.

The third stage begins in 1998. During this period, the process of monopolization of the media in Kazakhstan began. For example, in 1997, 20 of the 40 or so television channels were shut down. Large industrial and financial groups, which have effectively used the government's restrictive measures, have begun to divide the media market in Kazakhstan. This process continues to this day "[10,64], - writes the scientist A.Ramazan.

Of the five Central Asian countries, only Kazakhstan has so far adopted the Law on Information and Communication Networks [11]. However, the national legislation of other republics in the region contains elements of control over the activities of network users and owners of Internet projects. In this case, each republic went its own way. For example, in Uzbekistan, websites are equated with the media under Article 4 of the Media Law. It states that a publication that is published at least once every six months is considered a media outlet. Then, if the resource is updated in its area every six months, it is automatically considered a media representative.

Uzbekistan is preparing legislation to regulate the public Internet. Positive material about online censorship is published in the press. Therefore, the issue of stopping useless sites

is on the agenda. In this regard, it can be expected that restrictions on access to information will increase in Uzbekistan.

In Tajikistan, the law on the press and other media is not subject to legal regulation. It officially deals with the concepts of media and the Internet separately and does not correspond to each other.

As for Kyrgyzstan, the Internet is not equal to the media, but this topic is constantly raised. The government has proposed adding "publicly available information disseminated through computer networks" to the media. Over the past 7 years, there have been three attempts by different groups to equate the Internet with the media. Kyrgyzstan is the first country in Central Asia to consider rural areas as a separate segment in the development of ICT. The program for the development of information and communication services in rural areas until 2010 provides for 20 goals.

In all encyclopedic dictionaries and reference books on journalism, it is interpreted as a periodic dissemination of a topical issue or information through the media and a form of propaganda. It is said that the audience of journalism is an active member of the political, economic, spiritual and ideological life of society, which expresses its social significance, its relation to the phenomenon and reality. An online journalist is a type of public service that periodically disseminates, prepares and collects relevant information via the Internet as a means of mass communication. News sites are producing and disseminating information on the Internet at a very high speed. It expands the range of recipients and users of information from all over the world, regardless of where they live or where they live.

4.Results. Today in Kazakhstan, online newspapers are published every day in a new format. Unfortunately, the information in them is constantly updated.

According to Tatiana Startseva, CEO of TNS Central Asia, in 2018, 61% of Kazakhstanis watch TV every day, and 91% watch it every month. In 2013-2017, the share of the audience decreased by 43% in 34 years, and in 2018 it fell by another 12%.

The decline is also due to the territory of settlements and age differences. That is, the younger the age of the audience, the more content is consumed via the Internet [12].

Next, we decided to focus on the impact of new media on the system of genres. In Kazakhstan, the number of online newspapers is growing day by day. Among them we review the most professional online newspapers.

In the online newspaper "Minber" information is reflected in the genres of reports, interviews, reports. All kinds of journalistic genres can be found on the pages of the "Minber". Newspaper "Photo report", "Video", "Best". Comments. In the "Latest" posts, the best in terms of news, videos, photos, statistics will be selected.

The newspaper "Minber" provides flashcards with the help of flash technology, where the main problems and information are presented. The newspaper also has a special page on several social networks. Opportunities to leave a comment are considered, and it is marked next to the article to determine the rating.

Each column of the "Minber" is based on one theme. In particular, the "King of the Word" section publishes only news from the literary world, while the "Spirit" section publishes articles on patriotic education. The "Lawyer's Council" provides questions and answers to an online lawyer.

The section "Society" analyzes repatriates, economy, nation, land, water, social issues. For example, in January of this year, a number of Internet and traditional press editors commented on a threatening letter from the editor-in-chief of the information portal "Abai.kz" D. Kuat on behalf of the site "Kazaitys". The survey was read 357 times and was widely discussed among readers on social networks [13]. Of course, such disputes between

journalists can create a negative public image. However, we believe that those who violate journalistic ethics should be punished.

The online newspaper "Qazaq.kz" was launched on June 22, 2005 by the public association "Kazakh Internet". The main goal is to create a Kazakh-language Internet space. The head of the PA is Serikkazy Kokenayevich Kakibalanov. In 2006, one of the first online publications in our native language, the Internet newspaper "Kazakh" (www.qazaq.kz), launched the first Kazakh mail server and search engine. Since its inception, the PA has created more than 100 websites for the development of the Internet in our native language. The newspaper has headings "Society", "State", "Personality", "History", "Atadin". However, as we have seen in the newspapers, the information is updated only once a week.

The "Person" section of the online newspaper "Qazaq.kz" provides memoirs and essays about the lives of well-known or forgotten people. For example, in the memoirs and essays about the poet Tobagul, N. Shakenov, Irsymbet-Kazygul (Kazanbai batyr), T. Zholdyuly, interesting facts and unprecedented facts were published.

In the "History" section there are informative articles on national traditions, national interests, historical events, and in each issue of the newspaper there are excerpts from scientific works on the history of Kazakh newspapers.

The sites "Minber.kz", "Abai.kz" and "Zamandas.kz", which appeared in 2009, were created by the Foundation of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan for the development of the state language. In November 2009, the portal "Abai.kz" became the winner of the Kaznet "Award KZ". The site is used by more than 500 users a day. The content of these three sites is created by professional journalists working in traditional media. However, it is too early to comment on their place in Kaznet and the state of development of the Kazakh language on the Internet, as these resources have only recently appeared. Portals "Kerek info", "Degen eken" appeared for users as a platform for exchange of opinions and content, but due to financial difficulties they were not able to advertise the project and provide interesting basic content.

The national portal "Massagan" is the most popular resource. There are video files, discussion forums, news, prose and poetry, history, archeology, literature and linguistics, and if the user has created his own account, he can add friends and exchange internal correspondence.

The portal monitors Kazakh blogs and informs you about each post added to the blogs registered in this section. Due to the popularity of the portal, the Writers' Union of Kazakhstan and most journalists are registered there. They also create their own content, which allows young publicists to interact with each other and directly with readers and learn from adults.

The sections of prose and poetry are similar to the runic resource "Prosa.ru". The portal "Massagan.kz" annually holds competitions among users and gives prizes to the winners. According to the portal administrator Bakhytnur Baiteli, their site is visited by 30,000 users a day. Due to the large number of people, the server often crashes, so access to the portal is sometimes difficult. The main audience of the portal is pupils and students. It is also used by writers, journalists and programmers.

According to the largest search engine Alexa.com, which keeps statistics on the traffic of WEB sites, the main part of the audience of the portal "Massagan" is young people studying at universities. These are students from Kazakhstan, Turkey, Mongolia, China and other countries. The portal's search engine uses Google traffic. The portal can be called an entertainment and entertainment Internet project.

Some have compared the media to a telegraph replaced by a telephone. However, instead of replacing the media, we should simply be able to supplement it with new media.

For example, our newspaper "Egemen Qazaqstan" is not only sold in newsstands, but also available on their website. The page "Egemen.kz" is updated throughout the day and sent to readers in real time.

In the last few years, the media has undergone a massive change, all the photos, animations, television, movies, newspapers have changed. Computer communications, e-mail, discussion forums, teleconferences, blogs, image-based virtual worlds have all been completely updated. Looking at it this way, the Internet has changed our lives 360 degrees. Even consumption itself is very different.

New media cannot survive without the transition from analog to digital technologies, because the new types of media we know are based on digital technologies. Digital media is designed to read digital codes. The most commonly used number system is a binary code that converts information to 0 and 1. A common code system means that any machine that can read binary code understands, stores, and processes information. Analog media loads information into an object by encoding it.

SMM is an integral part of Kazakhstan's new media. SMM (Social Media Marketing) is a tool for internet marketing. One of the main goals of this industry is to find consumers on the Internet. Also, the formation of the brand of the company or individual, increase sales of products or services through "Facebook", "Twitter", "Google+" and other blog platforms (yvision.kz, kerekinfo.kz, etc.) [13].

Salem Social Media is trying to work in all directions on YouTube. As you can see, web stories, talk shows, comedy programs, news from the Internet world and interview programs dominate. Every project tries to involve a well-known blogger, media personality or presenters and journalists. For example, the talk show "Salem Show" is held in the format of the TV program "Night Studio". Popular singer, actress and TV presenter Zhanar Aizhanova was invited as a moderator, and her readiness to experiment with new content can be seen in her surprising appearances. Another example is Aman Tasygan Live. Having gained experience in television, the strong journalist created programs on Internet television and attracted the attention of viewers. Currently, Salem is the largest project of Social Media in the Kazakh language. In the first issue of his project "Newold Kazakhs", which opened only a year ago, "Is television worn out, is YouTube ahead?" The plight of traditional Kazakh television was discussed in the issue. In other words, there was talk about topics that could not be talked about on television.

Salem Social Media includes three factors that ensure the development of Internet television: unique content, quality and multi-channel. It attracts the attention of the public through materials with different content that traditional TV channels do not show. High quality shooting and editing of content and the ability to emphasize the visual accent play an important role here. In addition, the development of critical programs in different areas, not limited to one project, brings them to the top of Kazakhstani content.

When considering the new media development trends in Kazakhstan, we noticed the following problem. It is the low quality of statistical services in determining and evaluating the ranking of information sites. We decided to discuss this issue in detail below.

Currently, the number of Kazakhstani information dissemination sites and official portals has sharply increased. For example, in 2005 and 2009, Google Analytics and Yandex.Metrics were among the most popular statistical services that determine the ranking of websites. However, e-commerce in Kazakhstan was formed even earlier. Even though the world trends are 3-5 years behind us, we can see that a lot of news is formed, even at zero level. We can connect the same problem with the penetration of new media into our society. For example, in order to determine the movement of the business, to evaluate its effectiveness, and most importantly, to determine the benefits of this efficiency to the

individual consumer, it is necessary to have a service that calculates all the data. All these goals were created by the resource liveinternet.ru. The site owner receives data every day, month and year from the moment of entering the calculator code. How many questions came, what is the most interesting or important of them? What pages are popular? We get clear answers to the question of how many people are on the site right now, most of them are from which region or city. Such a calculator is essential for determining the external effectiveness of the site. It also helps to determine what information needs to be disseminated more often as a result of an objective indicator or to put it into circulation faster. Unfortunately, such activities are carried out outside Kazakhstan.

In 2002, the first Kazakhstani Internet statistics zero.kz appeared. It was created to create a service outside of Kazakhstan and to calculate the Kazakhstani Internet system. Zero.kz was founded by Alexander Uskov, the only long-running statistical site for active Neolabs participants Dmitry Zimin and Vladimir Turekhanov. It is aimed at the Kazakhstan market. Today, more than 9,000 sites of various directions and scales in the country are connected to this computer. This figure made his work even more difficult. The meter reading is not enough for a qualitative analysis of the audience. Some hardware of the site is outdated. There are at least five statistical services that provide complete and accurate information. These include Google Analytics (USA), Chartbeat (USA), Alexa Internet (USA), Similarweb (UK) and Yandex.Metrica (Russia). In addition, most of Similarweb is open and accessible to the public. Due to the increase in the number of alternative services that can provide accurate and complete information to users between 2009 and 2013, many sites are abandoning it due to the technical problems of Zero.kz. Currently, the index of the top 10 most popular sites in Kazakhstan does not match Zero.kz. Unfortunately, the most popular resources Nur.kz, gismeteo.kz, Kolesa | Krisha | Market, Tengrinews.kz, OLX, 365info.kz refused the counter.

Another important issue in the development of new media is information security, detection and combating false information. Taking advantage of the global coronavirus pandemic, scammers have sent 18 million emails a day to users of Gmail, which has 1.5 billion users, with false information about Covid-19. According to Google, the pandemic has reached the peak of phishing attacks, and cybercriminals have tried to obtain users' personal information. The company claims to be able to block 99.9% of 100 million phishing emails per day using machine analytics tools [15]. During the pandemic, the World Health Organization, on behalf of government agencies, provided social support packages and instructed to fill in the personal data required to obtain it.

False information based on a social network and its services requires, first of all, the ability to think critically in order to build media literacy. However, first of all, it is necessary to clearly understand the specifics of cyberspace. In addition to the benefits of the Internet, such as interactivity, accessibility and transparency, the public should be fully aware of the dissemination of false information, attempts to influence the views of users, and build the ability to defend themselves. At the same time, improving critical thinking will be the most important tool in the fight against misinformation. It is necessary to increase the sense of responsibility in cyberspace among the representatives of public institutions. Every user should think about how to use the social network, be aware of the consequences of their actions and learn to accept feedback about themselves. The development of ethics also plays an important role in the formation of media literacy.

A variety of cyber threats can be prevented if every consumer of information gets acquainted with the facts, checks the sources and tries to control the process of selection, reception and distribution of the content he consumes.

Therefore, media literacy is the ability to make decisions and prevent changes and problems in human society with the advent of new technologies.

While information literacy focuses on the importance of access to information, its value, and the ethics of use, media literacy teaches the skills to understand the functions of the media, to evaluate the quality of those functions, and to communicate rationally with the media.

The media often has a direct influence on the manipulation of society by official organizations. This is due to the hasty dissemination of information, with an emphasis on the rapid dissemination of information, with minor changes to the "press releases" provided by organizations. Dissemination of such unverified, one-sided information to the public has been called "press release" [16, p. 23].

During the Coronavirus pandemic, cyber-attacks and fake information increased so much on Facebook that a new term, "infodemia," was coined. Even among the official media, the website Aikyn.kz published an article entitled "A drug that cures coronavirus in just two days was found" [17]. According to Fackcheck.kz, this is only a prediction of the experience at Monash University. The suppression of such information manipulation is primarily suspected and requires a thorough investigation of the sources.

Thanks to the available functions of digital technologies, in addition to the general effectiveness of cyberspace, in order to prevent the plans of groups intending to commit provocations, fraud and theft, the organization of measures to protect public safety in cyberspace at the state level since 2018. The adoption of the concept of "Cyber Shield" and the establishment of the Committee on Information Security under the Ministry of Digital Development, Innovation and Aerospace of the Republic of Kazakhstan was a concrete step in defining the cyber border of Kazakhstan.

Earlier, on November 14, 2011, on the initiative of President Nursultan Nazarbayev, the strategic directions of information security in the Republic of Kazakhstan until 2016 were approved. The study of optimal mechanisms to ensure information security in the context of digital technologies and socio-political issues has continued to develop on three main formulas:

1. legislative and normative-methodical;
2. organizational and managerial and organizational and technical;
3. personnel reserve;

At the same time, with the direct involvement of law enforcement agencies, regular monitoring was carried out to identify and prevent the facts on the Internet that promote religious extremism and terrorism. As a result, the distribution of 771 propaganda resources between 2011 and 2016 was blocked by the courts. A total of 1,073 cyber-acts attempting to publish materials inciting terrorism and religious extremism, ethnic tensions, and the violation of the rights of children and women were identified, monitored, and blocked [18].

Such comprehensive analysis measures were also mentioned in the special documents on combating religious extremism and terrorism in the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2013-2017, adopted in September 2013. It was clearly necessary to adopt appropriate legislation to implement comprehensive measures to combat cyber incidents. In this regard, in April 2014, the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Communications" was supplemented with Article 41-1 "On the procedure for termination of communication networks and facilities." Also, on April 23, 2014, Article 242-1 "Dissemination of false information" was added to the Criminal Code, which provides for the use of information and communication networks as one of the objects of control and analysis [19].

For the proper functioning of the "Kazakhstan Cyber Shield", special law enforcement units specializing in cyber security must be formed. This is a requirement tested in world practice. In other words, monitoring the legal relations in the domestic cyberspace with the help of technical systems, identifying and prosecuting those behind the incidents should be on

a par with offline security. This, in turn, will increase the responsibility of citizens in cyberspace.

Over the past 2-3 years, the number of cases of spreading unfounded false information on the Internet and causing panic in the country has increased significantly. False statements on social media are especially common in emergencies and emergencies. Accordingly, legal liability has increased. Such incidents have been punishable in the Criminal and Administrative Codes since 2015, ranging from a fine of 20 monthly calculation indices to 2-7 years in prison [20].

On May 11, 2018, the Center for International Journalism MediaNet, with the support of the Soros Foundation-Kazakhstan, launched the first fact-checking and fact-checking project in Central Asia and Kazakhstan, Factcheck.kz. Although it has not been established for a long time, it is concluded at the end of each year. The first steps were taken in September when a contract was signed with Factcheck.kz Project Syndicate. Since then, readers have gained access to previously unpublished Project Syndicate content related to fact-checking, ie analysis and verification of information, analytical materials on the world economy. The Factcheck.kz project has joined the ranks of fact-checking resources in the world. Specifically, reporterslab.org was one of the first to collect data on fact-checking in Kazakhstan and put it on its map. The year 2017 was marked by the detection of a number of public statements. We have noticed that the statistics of materials are often false. In short, information security is important for the state, and improving media literacy is a very important issue for professionals and consumers of information. Mastering media literacy, especially from kindergarten to the elderly, is a key challenge today.

5. Conclusion. Considering the main trends in the development of new media in Kazakhstan, we identified the following issues. First, the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Ministry of Information and Social Development of the Republic of Kazakhstan, as well as the Ministry of Digital Development, Defense and Aerospace Industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan will carry out the development of new media. Second, competitiveness in the media space has increased. We associate it with the increase in the number of registered media outlets in Kazakhstan. There are also various mobile applications and a digital magazine. We would like to introduce some of them. Applications only for Kazakhstanis:

The program "Air KZ" will be launched in January 2018 under the guidance of Kazhydromet. This application provides complete monitoring of ambient air quality in Kazakhstan to your mobile phone. According to the developers, the application can monitor the quality of ambient air throughout Kazakhstan. The sections of the appendix provide information on 46 settlements and 84 ecological stations. The "Air KZ" application is available on "iOS" and "Android" media.

A mobile version of the library "Kitap" has been developed. If you have an app installed on your mobile phone, you can download your favorite book and read it without connecting to the Internet. The application is free to install and 4,000 books are stored in the program memory. You can read any book in E-PUB format. The main page of the application presents "recently read books", "most popular books" and "most popular authors". The Kitap mobile application is adapted to the most popular models of smartphones and is available on Android and iOS platforms.

"Soyle.kz" is an application for learning the Kazakh language. There are 20 lessons in the Kazakh language in the program, and each user can start at their own level and monitor the development process through the application. The application also has a system that checks the correct construction, spelling and pronunciation of sentences. The program includes thematic conversations, game lessons, as well as ready-made phrases that can be

useful for those who do not know the Kazakh language in the hospital, bank, hotel, shop or while traveling. The application is available for "Android" and "iOS" based devices.

The "Smart Travel KZ" application was launched by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Kazakhstan for our compatriots abroad. The main purpose of the application "Smart Travel KZ" is designed to ensure the safety of citizens of Kazakhstan abroad, as well as to provide assistance and assistance abroad. The "Smart Travel KZ" application contains regional features of countries, norms of behavior, recommendations on actions in dangerous situations, emergency warnings and other necessary information for citizens abroad [21].

In conclusion, the development of new media in Kazakhstan is being carried out in stages. Of course, there are problems. First of all, the main task is to train convergent journalists who have mastered the possibilities of new media. Only then will the potential of the Kazakh media space increase and become more competitive. In this regard, it is important to undertake research projects on this topic in higher education.

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SELF-EDUCATION OF A TEACHER IS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN THE TRAINING OF COMPETITIVE SPECIALISTS IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION

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Annotation. The article presents the system of work of college teachers training specialists in the field of education and describes the advantages of such work, the influence of active methods on the development of functional literacy and creative abilities of students.

Keywords: self-education, the sphere of education, training of young specialists, teaching competence, active methods, functional literacy of students, competitiveness of graduates.

Педагог на протяжении всей жизни учится всему, так как в лицах его студентов перед ним каждый год сменяются временные этапы, углубляются и даже меняются представления о нашем мире. Самообразование не только важный фактор в работе, но и необходимый, ведь способность к самообразованию не формируется у преподавателя вместе с получением своего диплома об образовании. Эта способность определена психологическими и интеллектуальными показателями каждого отдельного преподавателя, но кроме этого и вырабатывается в процессе работы с источниками информации, анализа и самоанализа, мониторинга своей деятельности и деятельности коллег.

Уровень подготовки конкурентоспособных специалистов в сфере образования напрямую зависит от качества подготовки преподавателей учебного заведения. Обязательно этот уровень должен расти, и тут эффективность различных курсов повышения квалификации, семинаров и конференций невелика без процесса самообразования педагога.

Педагогический словарь дает определение: «Самообразование, целенаправленная познавательная деятельность, управляемая самой личностью; приобретение систематических знаний в какой-либо области науки, техники, культуры, политической жизни и т.п. В основе самообразования - интерес занимающегося в органическом сочетании с самостоятельным изучением материала».

(источник: педагогический словарь на сайте dictionary.fio.ru)

Если речь идет о самообразовании, то можно считать, что процесс образования осуществляется добровольно, сознательно, планируется, управляется и контролируется самим преподавателем.

Зачастую способности педагога к самообразованию бывают высоки, но не всегда реализуются на практике. Причинами, которые чаще всего мешают преподавателям заниматься самообразованием – это отсутствие времени, нехватка источников информации, отсутствие стимулов, отсутствие доступа к источникам информации, особенно к Интернету и др. Но это всего лишь проявление инертности мышления и лени ума, так как самосовершенствование должно быть неотъемлемой потребностью каждого педагога.

Наука и образование изменяются стремительными темпами, откладывая на мировоззрение студентов особый отпечаток, и соответственно, очень часто, формируют образ преподавателя как «несовременного человека». Учитель, педагог – профессия творческая. Именно творческий человек не может из года в год работать по одному и тому же поурочному плану, читать одни и те же лекции.

Не секрет, что многие родители и дети, выбирая будущую профессию, обязательно обращают внимание на педагогический состав учебного заведения. Преподавателю не безразлично, считают его «хорошим» или «плохим». Плохим педагогом быть обидно.

В Атырауском гуманитарном колледже имени Катиры Дутбаевой, работа по самообразованию и повышению квалификации преподавателей стоит на первом месте, так как колледж готовит не просто специалистов среднего звена, а учителей начальных и средних классов общеобразовательных школ. Представляя работу педагога в области самообразования, то можно определить это списком глаголов: читать, изучать, апробировать, исследовать, анализировать, наблюдать и писать.

Основными профессиональными направлениями самосовершенствования и самообразования считаем:

1. Психолого-педагогическое (ориентированное на студентов и родителей)
2. Психологическое (имидж, общение, искусство влияния, лидерские качества и др.)
3. Методическое (педагогические технологии, формы, методы и приемы обучения)
4. Правовое
5. Эстетическое (гуманитарное)
6. Историческое
7. Иностранные языки
8. Информационно-компьютерные технологии

В педагогическом процессе самообразования используются формы: индивидуальные - инициатором является сам преподаватель, однако руководители методических и административных структур иницируют и стимулируют этот процесс (самыми сильными педагогами именно в индивидуальном развитии мы считаем – Аскарова А.К., Рабай К.Т., и др.); и групповая – в виде деятельности методического объединения, семинаров, практикумов, курсов повышения квалификации обеспечивает обратную связь между результатами индивидуального самообразования и самим преподавателем (работа в команде сильна у преподавателей ПЦК педагогики, психологии и методики частных дисциплин и ПЦК русского языка и литературы).

Чтение конкретных педагогических периодических изданий, чтение методической, педагогической и предметной литературы, обзор в Интернете информации по преподаваемому предмету, педагогике, психологии, педагогических технологий, решение задач, упражнений, тестов, кроссвордов и других заданий по своему предмету повышенной сложности, или нестандартной формы все это является основными видами деятельности по самообразованию. Большое значение имеет посещение семинаров, тренингов, конференций, уроков коллег, проведение дискуссии, совещания, обмен опытом с коллегами. Мы практикуем изучение современных психологических методик в процессе интерактивных тренингов, педагоги иностранных языков изучают иностранные языки через чтения информации о достижениях мировой педагогики в прямых источниках.

Работа по систематическому прохождению курсов повышения квалификации, проведению открытых уроков для анализа со стороны коллег, организация кружковой и внеклассной деятельности по предмету в колледже налажена на достаточно высоком уровне.

Владение информационно-компьютерными технологиями не стоит на месте, с развитием этой сферы мы идем в ногу с ними. Занятия педагогов проходят с использованием электронных платформ высокого уровня.

Наши коллеги следят за проведением предметных выставок и тематических экскурсий по предмету. Взаимообучение, работа в образовательной среде тоже дает толчок к саморазвитию, самообразованию. И тут, появился такой термин как самообразование. Стимулом является собственные достижения.

Профессиональному росту ничего не должно мешать, а главным препятствием может стать болезнь. Поэтому, ведение здорового образа жизни, занятия спортом - это неотъемлемая часть в достижение результата.

Так что же дает самообразование педагогу? Это прежде всего повышение уровня и качества преподавания предмета, разработка и издание методических пособий, статей, учебников, программ, сценариев, появление новых форм работы, мастер-классов, обобщение опыта.

В нашем колледже нет деления кто должен заниматься самообразованием. Участником процесса самообразования являются директор (А.С.Карабаева), завучи по учебным и воспитательным процессам, руководители структурных подразделений, методисты, председатели методических объединений, педагогический коллектив

Методисты и руководители предметно-цикловых комиссий прослеживают своевременный подбор темы, личного плана самообразования преподавателя, контролируют за выполнением этапов работы. Организацию отчетных работ проводим в форме обобщения опыта, докладов, сбора и анализа отчетной документации, презентации результатов работ перед педагогическим коллективом, а также проводятся конкурсы педагогического мастерства («Лучший преподаватель», «Лучший куратор», «Лучший панорамный урок» и тп). За рамками педколлектива показываем лучшие свои наработки. Все эти мероприятия не только помогают педагогу вовремя пройти аттестацию, но и получить квалификационную категорию, которая стимулируется дополнительными надбавками к зарплате.

В нашем колледже предметно-цикловые комиссии (ПЦК) работают грамотно, систематически и эффективно, в начале каждого учебного года все преподаватели выбирают «Тему, над которой работает преподаватель» и фиксируют эту тему в планах ПЦК.

На основе выбранной темы педагог разрабатывает личный план работы над поставленной перед собой проблемой. Структура плана: тема, цели и задачи, гипотеза и предполагаемый результат, этапы и сроки выполнения, все действия и мероприятия, проводимые в процессе, форма отчета.

Уже заключительным этапом будет отчет с анализом и выводами над темой. Для использования этого опыта сам педагог пишет рекомендации для коллег.

Конкурентноспособность человека на рынке труда, как известно, во многом зависит от его способности овладевать новыми технологиями, адаптироваться к изменяющимся условиям труда, поэтому важно использование технологии «портфолио учителя» для педагогического коллектива, особенно для вновь аттестуемых учителей.

Наиболее результативным способом поделиться результатами своего творческого педагогического опыта является размещение материалов в сети. Это позволяет учителю создать некую виртуальную библиотеку и дает коллегам со всего света могут увидеть и использовать результаты, поделиться отзывами и получить дальнейший толчок к развитию. В таком случае педагогический опыт становится общедоступным во времени и пространстве.

Информационно-коммуникативные технологии не могут вытеснить традиционные методы, они только нам позволяют приблизить обучение к сегодняшним реалиям. Поэтому, самообразование помогает совершенствованию методов работы,. В настоящее время одной из наиболее актуальных задач системы педагогического

образования является формирование информационно-коммуникационной компетентности (ИКК) преподавателя, функциональной грамотности всех членов образовательного процесса. Участники образовательного процесса должны получить доступ к информационным ресурсам на различных носителях, в том числе и к сети Интернет. В связи с этим созданы условия для повышения квалификации педагогов, есть площадка для реализации индивидуальности, творчества.

Самообразование преподавателя колледжа, который готовит будущих учителей, напрямую связано с саморазвитием студентов. Именно этому, в нашем колледже традиционно уделяется большое внимание. Продолжая опыт «Педагогической мастерской», о которой мы не раз рассказывали на различных площадках, студенты готовят творческие отчетные конференции. Самообразование преподавателей, самосовершенствование и развитие студентов играют весомую роль в подготовке конкурентоспособных специалистов в области образования. И только в процессе самообразования и самосовершенствования педагог осваивает современные активные методы и использует их на занятиях и в работе со студентами. Невозможно работать по старым стандартам. Невозможно быть учителем старой формации. Использование активных современных методов работы — это часть самообразования педагога. Это влияет и на имидж преподавателя, и на качество образования.

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NEEDS ANALYSIS IN ESP FOR MOBILE COMPUTING IN TERMS OF BLENDED EDUCATION

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Abstract

The provided research illustrates the results of conducted needs analysis of a major that is related to information systems sphere, namely “Mobile Computing”, where English for Specific Purposes is studied as a foreign language. The necessity of collecting the data and analyzing it was due to designing a proper course curriculum that would be primarily focused on students’ needs, considering their aims and objectives should match the course’s outcomes; and to approaching suitable techniques that would assist in achieving those aims. Distance learning due to COVID-19 restrictions challenged the author in developing a syllabus that would contemplate the mentioned above factors and aspects reckoned for an academic year. As it is believed that distance learning will take place for an obscure period, the actuality of the provided research is expected to be significant for the nearest two years. After this period, the research is estimated to be renovated.

1. Introduction

The research is provided due to the novelty of study, ESP for Mobile Computing is not deeply examined yet, and the curriculum is primarily based on ESP for Information Systems and Information Technologies. English for Specific Purposes (ESP) according to the 4th edition of *Longman dictionary of language teaching and applied linguistics* is defined as “the role of English in a language course or program of instruction in which the content and aims of the course are fixed by the specific needs of a particular group of learners” (Richards & Schmidt, 2010), i.e., needs analysis of a certain major students should be the basis of ESP.

Needs analysis (NA) is a considerable factor in ESP that contributes to a proper curriculum and syllabus design based on learner-centered education. This factor had become far more actual and valuable during the transmission of a learning process from the traditional to a blended due to COVID-19 pandemic. It was necessary to take into account the change in the usual format of education, keeping the students’ focus on the learning process, their involvement and interest in the subject, as well as the performance of an independent work, and competently approach the quantity and quality of the taught material for synchronous and asynchronous classes, for which it was necessary to obtain data by NA and create lessons considering them.

NA is the procedure of getting information from potential students of ESP based on questionnaire that cover essential requirements like learning materials, teaching approach and strategies, course expectations and outcomes, methodology. As well as course content and topics, language materials and independent works, dates and deadlines, synchronous/asynchronous study tools and platforms. After collecting the results and analyzing them, the institution represented by the lecturers can identify not only what should be implemented and improved, but also how to achieve it effectively. In this occasion, providing blended education is considered in NA, the re-shaped curriculum should encourage students’ competence for independent learning. Generally speaking, NA is “the systematic collection and analysis of all subjective and objective information necessary to define and validate defensible curriculum purposes that satisfy the language learning requirements of

students within the context of particular institutions that influence the learning and teaching situation” (Brown, 1995).

NA implements four viewpoints on needs: (a) *democratic view* examines every element of the ESP majorities want, like *wants, desires, expectations, requests, motivations*; (b) *discrepancy view* scrutinizes the differences between what learners should be able to do in the ESP and what they currently can do, like *deficiencies, lacks, gaps, requirements*; (c) *analytic view* explores elements of the ESP that students should learn next based on SLA theory and experience, like *next step, algorithms of learning*; (d) diagnostic view assesses elements of the ESP that will cause problem if they are missing, like *necessities, essentials, prerequisites* (Brown, 2016, p13-14). The prior task for the ESP developer in that occasion should overlay three abilities necessary for successful communication in a professional target setting - usage of the particular jargon characteristic of occupational context, usage of more generalized set of academic skills, usage of language in everyday communication regardless of occupational context – that is very deep research demanding task (Gatehouse, 2001).

Concerning the analysis itself, NA in ESP in its turn has nine approaches (target analysis, present situation analysis, pedagogic needs analysis, discourse analysis, register analysis, genre analysis) and five components (target situation analysis, learning situation analysis, present situation analysis, means analysis, language audits) overall being described into 10 specific areas, which cover domain of language use, the students’ attitude towards the ESP curriculum, language skill learning preferences, the importance of particular language skills, the learning strategies preferences, the classroom interaction, the role relationship, the teaching activities preferences, the environmental situation, and the students’ need from the program (Brown, 2016, p19-20).

Blended learning is a combination of students’ self-study with synchronous interaction with a lecturer and, in some cases, individual assistance; this type of learning became compulsory in Kazakhstan since COVID-19 spread in March, 2020 and tends to continue by the end of the pandemic. To make blended learning successful technical issues should be taken into serious consideration, i.e., a video conference type which makes synchronous classes possible and capable, and a platform where study materials, tasks, assignments are to be uploaded and students to be marked, thus it should be technically reliable with data security provided, and available both for the lecturer and students. Various video conference tools could be applied in that conditions, namely ZOOM, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, etc. Learning platforms choice is also variable depending on the university, including Canvas, Platonus, Univer, Moodle, etc. The targeted group (MC) uses Skype, that is entirely user friendly with common instructions and opportunity to chat as a group or individually, however no break-out rooms are available there; Moodle is used as an asynchronous study platform.

ESP for Mobile Computing (MC) takes six credits in two semesters of an academic year. The curriculum for this program was commonly based on Information Systems and Information Engineering in Economics, that covered primary content and contained generalized learning objectives and outcomes, but they were no longer specific and definite with narrow direction of the major. The course aims of ESP for MC require students to develop and work out basic communication skills that are necessary for the successful performance of professional activities related to the search, processing and transmission of technical information in English. The course objectives include to teach students to: a) evaluate, analyze, annotate and summarize texts within the professional sphere of communication; b) communicate in English and understand the language of information systems realia, competently use scientific and technical terms in professional discussion; c) apply theoretical acquisition of technical terms into practice. The arranged syllabus had been

conducted for fifteen weeks. The current qualitative research utilizes a NA in the form of questionnaire to examine students' ESP needs and to assess a semester period.

MC students are multilingual, where L1 is Russian and it is most commonly spoken every day, L2 is Kazakh which they speak more or less when necessary, and English is their foreign language which they rarely speak in their daily life. However, as ESP is mainly referred for advanced level, the course's pre-requisite is B1-B2 General English, i.e., it is expected that MC students should acquire English at a higher level and this fact should have also been regarded in designing NA questionnaire. As there is no specific coursebook for ESP for Mobile Computing, the lecturer selects the materials from specific coursebooks for Information Systems, ICT, Telecom and IT; additional sources from websites and EAP (Writing) are also welcome. Thus, in this study an ESP NA for MC is undertaken to examine needs in a thorough fashion and to evaluate to what extent the materials accomplish the program's aims, objectives and outcomes.

2. Methods

To collect necessary data, it was decided to provide qualitative research, thereby a needs analysis questionnaire was developed by the researcher. The examined areas of English language teaching included the following: the present and future domains of language use and reason to study English; the learning preferences in terms of language skills; the importance of particular language skills; the preferred learning strategies; the students' needs from the course; additionally including blended learning peculiarities in studying English. To analyze the data, percentage analysis was used, so that figures could be analyzed qualitatively to have a holistic review. As the researcher has a small number of students on Mobile Computing major as a group, 7 students participated in the questionnaire. The questions and multiple-choice answers were designed simple and readable for them and it took 2 days to collect the data. The guidance on how to complete the questionnaire was provided beforehand in order to avoid misunderstanding.

3. Findings and discussions

The information provided below demonstrates the findings and discussion of the questionnaire results, where 15 questions with multiple-choice answers are stated and they are classified into five areas of ESP NA.

The first area to be analyzed is the present and future domains of language use and reason to study English. This area overlays in 4 questions which examines students' current level of English, their prior purpose of learning English, the sphere they could apply English except university classes, and the function of English in their nearest future. As Figure 1 illustrates, more than half of the group consider their levels to be Upper-Intermediate, as 57,1% claim their level is B2, which means language material should be adjusted accordingly, so that the lower-level students would not suffer and higher-level students would not lose interest.

Figure 1. Percentage result of question 1

The result of percentage analysis provided in Figure 2 demonstrates that the majority of students have the same purpose as it is expected in the course outcomes in the syllabus, where 42,8% are eager to acquire necessary knowledge and hard skills that will be applicable in their major. Career promotion in the prospective future, that is also a motivating stimulus to study English in Kazakhstan, follows the previous purpose with 28,6%. Then it can be seen, that 14,3% plan to continue studying abroad and to conduct research on a postgraduate degree; and socializing while travelling abroad also is equal in number. Thus, the purposes to study English and the proportion of answers are reasonable.

Figure 2. Percentage result of question 2

The present domain of language use is suggested in the question 3 and as Figure 3 shows that the majority of students claim that English is usable at studies to work with specific terms with 71,4%; and the rest of the students use English in entertaining industry.

Figure 3. Percentage result of question 3

The future domain of language use is presented in the question 4 and as Figure 4 indicates that more than half of the group definitely see the privilege of English knowledge in their future career promotion with 57,1%; some students claim that language will be necessary when travelling which they assume to be abroad with 28,6%; and the rest percentage refers to postgraduate studies and research to be conducted presumably in English.

Figure 4. Percentage result of question 4

The next area is students' needs from the course that is presented in the following questions, where question 5 is presented in Figure 5. It is illustrated that more than half of the group tend to acquire necessary knowledge and hard skills that will be applicable in their major with 57,2%, however the rest of the students want to understand basic technical terms.

Figure 5. Percentage result of question 5

Students' stimulus to study is represented in question 6 as it can be seen in Figure 6, where the prior motivation is intrinsic and seems to be very conscious, that is to expand the knowledge with 85,7%. In contrast, trivial stimulus to improve marks in extrinsic motivation has the lowest number which makes the research reasonable.

Figure 6. Percentage result of question 6

As there is no specific ESP coursebook for Mobile Computing major, it was deserving to inquire the date if the students need one as it can be seen in Figure 7. More than half of the group illustrate hesitation with 57,1%, that is, perhaps due to the additional resources and IS/IT based ESP coursebooks, that the lecturer relies to when conducting classes. 28,6% agree that they need a coursebook, which is worthy of institution's attention to consider in the following academic years.

Figure 7. Percentage result of question 7

The following area is referred to the preferred learning strategies where question 8 asks if students agree with emphasis on their independent work during blended learning as Figure 8 demonstrates. The opinions are contrasting, where more than half of the group with 57,2% disagree, and the minor half agree. It means that this question tends to be debatable.

Figure 8. Percentage result of question 8

Continuing with independent work it is necessary to investigate which amount of work students find feasible during the semester. So, question 9 shows the data that is indicated in Figure 9, where it can be seen that the majority of group agree that 4 independent works per semester is the norm, they can deal with showing 71,4%.

Figure 9. Percentage result of question 9

Now, when it is distinct with the amount of independent works, it is also essential to investigate which type of independent work the students find deserving and educating as it is illustrated in question 10 and Figure 10, where the majority select project works with 85,7%, and the following type is writing summaries with only 14,3%.

Figure 10. Percentage result of question 10

As NA examines the students’ learning preferences in strategies, it is necessary to find the topics of interest which is reflected in question 11 and the data is showed in Figure 11. Half of the group tend to study ESP for MC programming with emphasis on software with 42,8%, and equal figures with 28,6% is divided in two opinions like MC for technician with emphasis on field working and hardware and MC for social life with highlights on recent updates of tech news. As the answers are divided almost equally, this issue should be considered in designing the curriculum content and all of the mentioned topics should be included there.

Figure 11. Percentage result of question 11

Exploring students’ views and preferences in exercises and activities on English classes should also be taken into account, that is why question 12 covers this detail, and as Figure 12 indicates, 42,8% of students suggest to have discussions with peers and with the lecturer; the rest of the views is divided equally by 28,6% for project works and presentations (individual or in pairs). Thus, each of these activities in a moderate amount should be performed during the online classes. It is not surprising that “quizzes” answer tends to be an outsider, as it is a matter of stress and anxiety according to students’ personal interview replies.

Figure 12. Percentage result of question 12

The next area to be investigated is blended learning peculiarities in learning English, where question 13 asks about the number of synchronous (online) classes a week to acquire the level of English students expect to have. Figure 13 shows that two hours are enough with 71,4% of answers, while the rest of students require three hours.

Figure 13. Percentage result of question 13

Examining how well students operate with online learning platforms and video conferences is a matter of significance in blended learning, so the question 14 inquires how friendly are they with Skype and Moodle. The majority of group with 71,4% tend to feel very confident in using mentioned above digital tools, however there are still a number of students who sometimes find it troublesome looking for the right folder when downloading the class materials, as Figure 14 illustrates. Additional time to clarify those details should be regarded.

Figure 14. Percentage result of question 14

The last question (15) is dedicated to explore the area of the importance of particular language skills and it asks about the skills students need to improve on English classes. The answers are divided mildly, to be precise 42,8% claim that speaking is necessary to be developed; 28,6% think they should enrich their vocabulary; 14,3% of students refer to grammar and the same number is for developing listening skill, i.e., all of the mentioned skills need to be emphasized.

Figure 15. Percentage result of question 15

4. Conclusions and Suggestions

The collected data and provided analysis results have claimed that the students of ESP for Mobile Computing class anticipate English learning as an essential milestone in their academic background and current studies, being an important subject in their academic performance and an essential argument in their future career and academic perspectives, whether it is an international company or postgraduate research abroad. The study also illustrates that students tend to do independent work while blended learning rather than task-based learning, that should definitely be considered in curriculum design. However, due to a particular department in a specific place, the results and conclusion are limited and they can differ in another sphere and situation. Thus, further research of needs analysis for diverse spheres to be discussed is recommended.

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